

Innovative dissemination methods: Good practices and lessons learned

OPENing UP new methods, indicators and tools for peer review, impact measurement and dissemination of research results

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Abbreviations

AHSS – Arts, Humanities, and Social Sciences

CC – Creative Commons

DARIAH – Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities

HBP – Human Brain Project

HMT – Homer Multitext Project

ICT – Information and communications technology

KPI – Key Performance Indicator

MS – Milestone

NASA – National Aeronautics and Space Administration

OOR - OpenOnlineResearch

ORCID – Open Researcher and Contributor ID

PES – Public Engagement with Science

PI – Principal investigator

PPSR – Public Participation in Scientific Research

PUS – Public Understanding of Science

RePEc – Research Papers in Economics

RRI – Responsible Research and Innovation

SDSS – Sloan Digital Sky Survey

STEM – Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics

UCL – University College London

WP – Work Package

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Summary

OpenUP Work Package 4 aimed to investigate innovative ways of disseminating research outputs beyond traditional academic dissemination in different disciplines. Such ways include the dissemination of research results in traditional media (e.g. newspapers, TV), social media (e.g. via blogging), or museums, using text, images, videos, games, comics and other media formats. Such dissemination media and methods can support researchers in creating impact, help spread scientific results to wider audiences (e.g. the industry, policy makers, specialists outside the research community, journalists, the general public), as well as (in disseminating results via interactive Web tools) make transparent how research outputs are used in non-research communities and the general public, which can deliver further impact evidence relevant for researchers, funders and other stakeholders. Work within OpenUP addresses a variety of stakeholders, including researchers, institutions, funders, publishers, and citizens. To analyse the needs and attitudes of these groups, we employed multiple instruments including literature review, an extensive survey of European researchers, case studies of projects employing innovative dissemination methods, interactive workshops, and interviews.

This deliverable report synthesises work across the OpenUP project to investigate innovative dissemination to provide insights into current practices, classify and assess methods and tools, and provide scenario-based case studies. The identified practices and methods have been validated in cooperation with other work packages to analyse the influence of Open Science practices on the impact and visibility of research outputs. The report is structured as follows:

- **Section 1 “Project background”** contextualises the study by providing information about the wider aims of OpenUP.
- **Section 2 “What is innovative dissemination”** defines terms and introduces contextual frameworks that will inform the later discussion.
- **Section 3 “Trends in innovative dissemination”** gives an overview of developments and attitudes amongst stakeholders across a range of issues.
- **Section 4 “OpenUP activities and lessons learned”** details the main findings from work done to conduct primary research (OpenUP Pilots) in the area of innovative dissemination, map requirements for communicating to particular stakeholders, investigate the link between alternative metrics and innovative dissemination, and create training and support resources.
- **Section 5 “Practical guidance for researchers and other stakeholders”** then condenses findings from across the project to provide systematic and easily implementable advice for researchers, research projects and research performing organisations interested in engaging in innovative dissemination.
- **Section 6 “Conclusions and outlook”** summarises the main findings of the report.

Key findings

By summarising the many rich strands of work conducted to investigate innovative dissemination and provide practical information for various stakeholders, this study reaches the following conclusions:

Dissemination is increasingly participatory and multi-directional: The OpenUP investigation of innovative dissemination methods revealed a wealth of approaches going beyond traditional academic publishing, and gathered success stories and good practices from all over the world. In particular, the analysis demonstrated the potential of digital technologies for involving audiences beyond the usual dissemination targets to actively involve peers or citizens that would otherwise be out of reach. Dissemination in an open science context is increasingly done at earlier stages of the research lifecycle and is thus becoming an integral part of the whole research workflow. In addition, dissemination becomes more interactive; as a result, it is often difficult to draw the line between the activities of dissemination and participation (see section 2.1.2). This was confirmed by our crowdsourcing of exam-

ples of innovative dissemination for the case studies. This activity connected OpenUP to peers in open science and in the research community, and informed them of the project goals and early results.

Innovative dissemination is integral to Open Science: Open Science is rooted in principles of participation and transparency, enabling others to collaborate in, contribute to, scrutinise and re-use research and spread knowledge as widely as possible. In order to accomplish this, a wide-range of research outputs and processes which were not formerly made available must now be made so. As such, innovative dissemination is a core aim of Open Science. However, when it comes to openness, even the most innovative dissemination efforts, such as the Pluto Fly-By may not provide materials that can be used, modified or shared. Hence, researchers need guidance in all aspects of Open Science, including choosing the right license for their materials in order to achieve the highest possible reuse of their materials.

A proliferation of channels: The variety of innovative dissemination methods found in the case studies was further broadened in the survey, where we received more than 100 descriptions of use of innovative dissemination methods and tools. There have never been more avenues for the dissemination of research, and yet researchers remain largely focused on just a few traditional outputs (journal articles, books, conference presentations).

Enthusiasm is not reflected in uptake: While we can observe enthusiastic uptake with specific groups of researchers, the OpenUP survey results also showed that there is a gap in practice when it comes to innovative dissemination. While we can observe enthusiastic uptake with specific groups of researchers, the survey results also showed that there is a gap in practice when it comes to innovative dissemination. Even though 71% of researchers agreed that it is important to disseminate to non-research audiences, all of the dissemination channels specifically designed for doing so are used only by less than a third of researchers on a regular basis. Communicating to a wider audience seems therefore to be more of a developing norm with enthusiastic early adopters than a widely exercised practice. This is emphasized by the fact that only 12% of respondents reported to having achieved an outstanding result using innovative dissemination channels. In addition, two thirds reported to start with the dissemination only after the conclusion of research. When asked about the reasons for not using innovative dissemination channels, next to organisational reasons (time, money, credit), lack of knowledge of innovative dissemination channels and methods is mentioned by 40% of respondents. This share is even higher for young researchers.

Gender and diversity are vital elements: Success in research and innovation is best served by the efficient contribution of all useful viewpoints. Ensuring that all voices get heard despite ongoing social biases and inequities in distribution of resources requires respecting diversity in science. With respect to gender, for example, we have identified four relevant aspects: (1) the gender distribution within the team responsible for research and dissemination, (2) representation of gender in the disseminated materials, (3) gender sensitivity and inclusiveness of the used dissemination tools, platforms and strategies, and (4) gender aspect related to the target audience.

The importance of systematic experimentation with new methods of innovative dissemination: The technological and social conditions for the dissemination of research are evolving so quickly that it is essential that researchers and research support services (e.g., libraries) remain alert to new possibilities and willing to systematically investigate possible issues in implementation – as with, for example, our investigation of needed standards and practices for data publishing.

The need for advice tailored to particular stakeholders: In scoping the needs for disseminating to businesses and the public, it has become clear that a diverse approach for defining and supporting open science dissemination is needed. There is no one size fits all. The division in the two above mentioned target groups has proven not to be necessarily evident or useful for all projects. The division into these two main target groups is rather arbitrary and cannot necessarily be applied to other specif-

ic target groups. A more diverse approach to defining and supporting open science dissemination is needed (e.g. including other target groups or addressing trans-disciplinary questions).

The link between alternative metrics and innovative dissemination: Alternative metrics provide efficient feedback on the success or otherwise of many innovative dissemination activities. Interpreting these statistics, however, requires not only familiarity with platforms which deliver such metrics, but also with the ways in which they are calculated and the ways in which they might misrepresent real impact. Hence, better training and awareness of alternative metrics will enhance successful take-up of innovative dissemination.

Uptake can be fostered through training and support activities: Training and awareness activities are vital in alerting researchers and others of the value of innovative dissemination. Funders and research organisations can incorporate such training into other activities. Hence, integrating simple steps into research processes will embed innovative dissemination in scholarly workflows. By presenting ten simple steps to innovative dissemination in the next section, we will attempt to show how small changes in research dissemination can have a large impact.

There is an urgent need to incentivise innovative dissemination: Novel dissemination practices are often not on the agendas of policy makers, national research funders or research institutions. Innovative dissemination activities not reflected in reward schemes which are still heavily skewed towards traditional outputs. In order to make such activities count in research life and hence foster uptake, rewards and incentives should be adjusted.

Innovative dissemination could be enabled by a new class of professionals: Targeted and interactive Open Science Communication should be supported on policy and institutional level to increase active participation by researchers. In this context, additional funding of science communication activities, setting appropriate incentives and providing communication and soft-skills training for researchers are key factors. To fill this gap, we propose to create new science communication roles and positions to be staffed with people both skilled in science communication and with science expert knowledge. It is important to have, next to Public Relations and marketing staff, trained experts with the necessary scientific background and skills, who are also trained in communicating to and interacting with audiences outside the research community by means of Web 2.0 technologies.

1. Project background

1.1 OpenUP project aims

Open Access and Open Scholarship have revolutionized the way scholarly artefacts are evaluated and published, while the introduction of new technologies and media in scientific workflows has changed the “how” and to “whom” science is communicated, and how stakeholders interact with the scientific community. The OpenUP project studied key aspects and challenges of the currently transforming science landscape to provide a cohesive framework for the review-disseminate-assess phases of the research life cycle that is fit to support and promote Open Science.

The OpenUP partners engaged in an overarching research exercise. It included landscape scans of literature and a Europe-wide survey of researchers on the key topics of the project, open peer review, innovative dissemination and altmetrics. The consortium reached out to the main experts and stakeholders in the review-assess-disseminate areas to gather their inputs on the current practices, challenges and the latest developments. OpenUP engaged with all the stakeholders via a series of outreach and training events, and a newly created OpenUP Information Hub. The OpenUP Hub is a collaborative web-based platform that hosts catalogue of open tools, services, methodologies, best practices from various disciplines and success stories that can be used by researchers, policy makers, funders and other interested parties. All the project’s results were tested through a series of pilots involving researchers from four scientific communities (Life Sciences, Social Sciences, Arts & Humanities, Energy). The final recommendations of the OpenUP project will be evidence-based and validated practical guidelines directed to the EU, national and institutional policy makers looking for ways to address the emerging challenges and adapt to the rapidly changing scientific research landscape.

Figure 1 OpenUP project methodology

1.2 Scope of this document

This study synthesises and validates work within OpenUP to analyse and expand the scope of innovative dissemination of research. It synthesises findings from work employing a diverse array of methods and sources (metrics, survey, interviews, workshops) that engage and address a range of stakeholder groups (e.g., researchers, journalists, citizens, funders, policy makers). It confirms our previous approaches and findings. The report makes clear the benefits of innovative dissemination, addresses the challenges stakeholders face in taking up these practices, and provides validated advice for researchers and policy makers to foster uptake.

The report is structured as follows:

- **Section 1 “Project background”** contextualises the study by providing information about the wider aims of OpenUP.
- **Section 2 “What is innovative dissemination”** defines terms and introduces contextual frameworks that will inform the later discussion.
- **Section 3 “Trends in innovative dissemination”** gives an overview of developments and attitudes amongst stakeholders across a range of issues.
- **Section 4 “OpenUP activities and lessons learned”** details the main findings from work done to create information resources (OpenUP Hub), training and awareness events and primary research (OpenUP Pilots) in the area of innovative dissemination.
- **Section 5 “Practical guidance for researchers and other stakeholders”** then condenses findings from across the project to provide systematic and easily implementable advice for researchers, research projects and research performing organisations interested in engaging in innovative dissemination.
- **Section 6 “Conclusions and outlook”** summarises the main findings of the report.

2. What is innovative dissemination?

Research dissemination, as defined by Wilson et al. (2010), is a planned process that involves consideration of target audiences, consideration of the settings in which research findings are to be received, and communicating and interacting with wider audiences in ways that will facilitate research uptake in decision-making processes and practice (where appropriate). Dissemination is therefore defined as an activity that can be targeted at academia as well as broader audiences. One of the crucial characteristics, however, is that dissemination facilitates research uptake and understanding.

As with all areas of life, research dissemination has been disrupted by the Internet and digitally-networked technologies. In addition, powerful trends towards responsible research and innovation, the globalisation of research, the emergence and inclusion of new or previously excluded stakeholders, and the advent of open science are reshaping the scope and nature of the target audiences and purposes of dissemination. Information and communications technology (ICT) has been embraced by researchers since the 1980s (Nentwich 2003). The Internet is no exception to this. ARPANET, the earliest precursor of the Internet, was funded by the Advanced Research Project Agency of the US Department of Defense, but it was first developed at University of California, Los Angeles (UCLA). Initial connections were made to other research universities such as Stanford and the University of Utah (Ruthfield 1995). E-mail, newsgroups, and mailing lists were soon picked up by researchers as a novel means of communication (Nentwich 2003). The World Wide Web was invented at CERN (Berners-Lee et al. 1994) and provided a convenient way for universities and researchers to create an online presence and to disseminate the results of their work.

It is therefore no surprise that dissemination of research has been changed considerably following the digitisation of science - and arguably to a higher degree than other steps in the research lifecycle. Over the years, publishers have moved journals online and converted them to e-journals. The open access and open science movements have transformed how research can be accessed and what types of outputs are being published. Most research findings are now disseminated in a way that is “born digital”.

In the wake of this transformation, innovative forms of research dissemination have emerged: blogging has become very popular among researchers, as has Twitter. Academic social networks boast millions of users. New formats of interacting with the public, such as science slams and TED talks are broadcast via YouTube around the world. Some researchers have even decided to make all of their research findings public in time by keeping an open notebook. OpenWetWare, a platform where researchers can document their results in a wiki system, has over 16,500 members who have contributed some 980,000 revisions to date¹.

But it is not only the increase in use of ICT that has had a profound effect on dissemination. The push towards public understanding of science and research since the 1980s, and an emphasis on engagement and participation of non-research audiences have brought about new forms of dissemination (Beaufort 2016). These approaches include popular science magazines and science shows on television and the radio. In recent years, new types of events have emerged that aim at involving the general public, including science slams and open lab days. With science cafés and hackerspaces, novel, participatory spaces for research production and dissemination are emerging.

Hence, the definition of *innovative dissemination* used in this report means dissemination that goes beyond traditional academic publishing (e.g. academic journals, books, or monographs) and meetings (conferences and workshops). As in traditional dissemination, it is necessary that research uptake and understanding are facilitated. Hence, a citizen science project which involves citizens in data collection but does not otherwise educate them about the research, is not here considered innovative dissemination.

¹ <http://www.openwetware.org/wiki/Special:Statistics>

2.1 Models of innovative dissemination

In this section, we look at the theories and models behind conceptual dissemination frameworks, with a focus on dissemination beyond academia.

2.1.1 Theories and models behind conceptual dissemination frameworks

Wilson et al. (2010) performed an extensive survey of conceptual dissemination frameworks in health sciences and social sciences. Of the 33 included frameworks that were deemed detailed enough to be actually used in practice, 28 were either implicitly or explicitly based on one or more of three theories: persuasive communication, diffusion of innovation and social marketing.

- **Persuasive communication**, the most popular theoretical approach in this study is based on the Communication-Persuasion Matrix (McGuire 2001). The matrix describes the process of being persuaded; it consists of five input communication factors and twelve output persuasion steps. The five input factors, which have an impact on the success of the communication, are: source, channel, message, audience, and setting. Frameworks that build on this approach encompass 3-5 of these factors.
- **Diffusion of innovation** (Rogers 1962) is the second most popular theory. According to Wilson et al. (2010), diffusion of innovation “offers a theory of how, why, and at what rate practices or innovations spread through defined populations and social systems. The theory proposes that there are intrinsic characteristics of new ideas or innovations that determine their rate of adoption, and that actual uptake occurs over time via a five-phase innovation-decision process (knowledge, persuasion, decision, implementation, and confirmation). The included frameworks are focused on the knowledge and persuasion stages of the innovation-decision process”
- **Social marketing** (Kotler and Zaltman 1971) also underpinned a number of studies; it represents an approach to planned social change, in which marketing concepts are applied to the problem of promoting social causes. It is defined as “the design, implementation and control of programs calculated to influence the acceptability of social ideas and involving considerations of product planning, pricing, communication, distribution, and marketing research.”

2.1.2 Dissemination beyond academia: from one-way to three-way communication

According to Beaufort (2016), there are three levels of disseminating research results to the public:

1. **“Public Understanding of Science” (PUS):** the idea behind public understanding of science is to make scientific findings more accessible to non-scientists. It started in the 1980s, when it became apparent that there was a crisis of confidence in research. PUS is characterized by one-way communication from scientists to the public. Examples are prime-time science shows on television.
2. **“Public Engagement with Science” (PES):** PES was born, when it became clear that one-way communication could not solve the issue of detachment between science and society. If the goal of PUS is the scientification of society, the goal of PES is the socialization of society. One-way communication is replaced by a dialogue between science and society. Research and research questions are seen in a societal context and are being discussed as such.
3. **“Public Participation in Scientific Research” (PPSR):** PPSR goes beyond information and discussion - its goal is that society actively participates in scientific research on a level playing field. PPSR is enabled by online communication and characterized by a three-way communication, where citizens talk to each other and with researchers (Bucchi and Trench 2014).

As an example, let's consider the approach of Responsible Research and Innovation Initiative (RRI) of the European Commission. RRI "is an approach that anticipates and assesses potential implications and societal expectations with regard to research and innovation, with the aim to foster the design of inclusive and sustainable research and innovation."² To reach this goal, RRI promotes public engagement with participatory elements. For example, it is foreseen that "societal actors (researchers, citizens, policy makers, business, third sector organisations, etc.) work together during the whole research and innovation process in order to better align both the process and its outcomes with the values, needs and expectations of society." One instrument in this context are participatory research actions. RRI can therefore be classified as a Stage 2 (PES) approach, with certain elements from Stage 3 (PPRS).

Finally, within an open science context, dissemination is increasingly done at earlier stages of the research lifecycle (Kraker et al., 2016). Dissemination is becoming an integral part of the whole research workflow and more interactive. As a result, it is often difficult to draw the line between the activities of dissemination and participation.

² <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/responsible-research-innovation>

3. The need to promote Innovative Dissemination

This section presents key findings from a number of surveys on dissemination to highlight key trends in attitudes towards and experiences with innovative dissemination, including the OpenUP survey undertaken in 2017. The picture painted creates the case for change: there is a will to disseminate research via novel channels and to new audiences, but this is hampered by a lack of training, support and incentives for these activities. Investing in these activities will increase the impact of research.

3.1 OpenUP survey (2017)

The OpenUP survey was conducted between 20 January and 23 February 2017 with an aim to capture current perceptions and practices in peer review, dissemination of research results and impact measurement among European researchers. It was implemented via online survey and directly targeted to mined contact details of the main authors of publications stored in arXiv, Pubmed and RePEc. The survey received 1347 responses, of which 976 were completed.

The survey results on questions involving innovative dissemination showed that the majority of the researchers (71%) agreed with the importance to disseminate their research to non-research audiences (Figure 2 below). However, only a minority of researchers stated they target non-academic audiences frequently and also dissemination channels specifically designed for doing so are used only by a small share of researchers on a regular basis. Only 12% of respondents reported to having achieved an outstanding result using innovative dissemination channels and two thirds reported to start with the dissemination only after the conclusion of research. These findings illustrate that communicating to a wider audience seems therefore to be more of a developing norm with enthusiastic early adopters than a widely exercised practice.

Figure 2 Overall share of respondents regarding dissemination to non-research audiences as very important or rather important. Source: OpenUP survey 2017

Some innovative dissemination tools were used more often than others, namely Open Access repositories, academic social networks and personal or project websites. In addition, there were some differences in dissemination tools use among researchers of different career stages and genders. A larger share of younger researchers used academic social networks and non-specialised social networks more frequently compared to more experienced respondents. The latter, on the other hand, showed a preference for a more frequent use of e-mails/newsletters and personal/project websites. Female re-

searchers reported more frequent use of events for the general public whereas more male researchers used open access repositories.

Researchers aiming to target non-academic audiences and disseminate to influence policymaking and practitioners engaged with several non-academic dissemination channels more frequently compared to the average respondent. These dissemination channels included popular science publications, events for the general public/specific target audiences other than researchers, press releases, academic social networks, non-specialist social networks and exhibitions and performances.

The respondents reported that the main barriers to practicing innovative dissemination mostly include organisational reasons (lack of time, insufficient funding and credit given for such activities). Also, lack of knowledge of innovative dissemination channels and methods was mentioned by 40% of researchers. More so among the young researchers compared to more experienced respondents.

Hence, we can sum the results from the OpenUP survey as showing that researchers are open to increasingly participatory, multi-directional dissemination, that there is a proliferation of channels in use, but that enthusiasm is not reflected in uptake. This shows an opportunity to educate further on innovative dissemination to reach a wider audience

The following subsections enrich these results with findings from previous studies.

Limited public engagement by researchersThe studies presented in this section investigated dissemination to the public from the researchers' and public engagement enablers' point of view. The first, "Factors affecting public engagement by researchers" came out of a project by a UK consortium (TNS-BMRB & PSI 2015), and represents an update to an earlier project by the Royal Society in 2006.

The empirical work consisted of a survey of 2,454 researchers and 269 public engagement enablers, as well as 50 qualitative interviews. As the title suggests, the understanding of dissemination is within the second stage of Beaufort's classification. Interestingly enough, the study also asked respondents as well what public engagement meant to them. 41% of researchers and 59% of enablers gave the answer "Interacting with the public/an audience/two-way dialogue".

The study reveals that 82% of researchers have engaged in a public engagement activity in a 12-month period, but it also notes that activity is often infrequent. The highest amount of activity can be seen for communication via social media, with 36% of researchers engaging in this activity four or more times, followed by giving a public lecture, which 48% of researchers did at least once. STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) researchers are less active in engaging in a public activity than AHSS (Arts, Humanities, and Social Sciences) researchers.

Nevertheless, the 2015 study observed a trend among STEM researchers to assign a higher importance to engagement with the public than in 2006 (see Figure 3 below). In addition, 53% of STEM researchers and 58% of AHSS researchers would like to spend more time engaging with the public.

"In relation to other things in your working life, how important is it for you to find time to engage with the public?"

Figure 3 Attitudes towards the value of public engagement (2006 & 2015). Source: TNS-BMRB & PSI (2015), © TNS 2015. Used with permission.

In terms of demographic features, the authors summarize that more senior staff, especially more senior female staff are most active in public engagement. In addition, those who have received training in public engagement and those who consider themselves well equipped in public engagement skills are more active than those who don't. The same applies to clinicians and respondents with a research and teaching contract.

When it comes to audiences, policy makers and politicians were seen as the most important audience to engage with by researchers (80%), followed by the general public and journalists/TV/radio. For enablers, these groups were of similar importance, along with young people in school and school teachers (84-87%). Industry and business followed not far behind (81%). It should be noted that the study did not question people, whether these were the audiences that they were actually engaging with.

Regarding perceived benefits, "Inform the public/raise awareness" took the top spot (51%), with ensuring that research is relevant (44%), maintaining public support for research (34%) and contributing to public debates (31%). When looking at AHSS researchers alone, the picture looks vastly different: contributing to public debates was mentioned most (54%), whereas maintaining public support for research received 20% and was only the fifth most mentioned benefit. With AHSS researchers, learning from public groups is the fourth most mentioned benefit (33%).

When asked whether researchers felt well equipped to engage with the public, two thirds reported that they were either very equipped (13%) or fairly equipped (53%). For STEM researchers, although feeling slightly less equipped to engage with the public than AHSS researchers, again a positive trend could be observed since 2006 (see Figure 4 below).

Finally, with regards to the barriers, the most important factor stopping researchers from getting more involved in public engagement were competing pressures on researchers' time (61%). Lack of opportunities/difficulty finding relevant audiences and not enough funding/difficulties getting funding came in on a joint second place (26%).

Figure 4 How well equipped do you feel to engage with the public on your research or subject? (2006 & 2015). Source: TNS-BMRB & PSI (2015), © TNS 2015. Used with permission

In the second study, Wilson et al. (2010) conducted a survey of 232 Principal investigators (PIs) of publicly-funded health research in the UK. The aim of the survey was to investigate dissemination practices of health researchers. The online questionnaire consisted of 36 questions to be answered within 30 minutes. Research dissemination was rated important or very important by 93% of respondents. The most important reasons for disseminating findings were to raise awareness of the findings (93%), to influence policy (85%) or practice (84%), to stimulate discussion/debate and to transfer research into practice (both 75%). 84% rated their dissemination activities as good or adequate, and less than 1% as excellent.

When asked about the dissemination channels, a majority named traditional dissemination channels, such as academic journals, conferences, and reports. It should be noted though that online dissemination was nowhere near where it is today: among the channels provided for selection were newsletters, e-mail alerts, CD-ROM and RSS feeds. An interesting finding is that researchers that have received advice/support from funders or within their department reported significantly more often that they had achieved an impact on policy. Two problems reported with dissemination were misrepresentation of research by third parties and lack of funding.

An opportunity to better disseminate researchThe European Commission (2013) coordinated a special Eurobarometer (public opinion survey) on Responsible research and Innovation (RRI), Science and Technology. This survey gives a complementary perspective from the public's side to the studies described above. Carried out in spring 2013, the survey involved face-to-face interviews of 27,563 respondents in the European Union and Croatia. It should be noted that interview questions were focused on science and technology, which - according to instructions in the survey - means "the natural sciences, like physics, chemistry, biology, and their application in technology and engineering, for instance computer technology, biotechnology and medical applications." The survey results are therefore not representative for the social sciences, humanities, and the arts.

The survey results show that there is an information gap: 53% of all Europeans are interested in developments in science and technology, although only 40% say they feel informed about them. This means that almost one in five Europeans are interested in developments in science and technology, but do not feel informed about them (18%). There is a strong correlation between interest and information: the higher the levels of interest in developments in science and technology, the higher the levels of feeling informed about such developments.

On the flipside, the survey shows that 40% of Europeans are neither interested nor informed. Furthermore, there is a divide between the North and East/South, between genders and education/occupation. Men are more likely to be interested in and feel informed about developments in science and technology than women are (64% vs. 44%). It is also more likely that they have studied any of these subjects at any education level (51% vs. 43%). This can be explained by the strict definition of science as natural sciences in the survey.

Television is the most mentioned source of information about developments in science and technology (65%), followed by the internet (35%) and newspapers (33%). Social media and blogs were mentioned by 10% as an information source. This is an interesting finding and may be attributed to the fact that the study was carried out four years ago. If the selection of information sources with regards to news was of any indication, we could see the following trends: over the last years, we have seen that those who prefer to read news have migrated online (Gottfried et al. 2016). When it comes to 18-24-year-olds, social media has overtaken television as the main news source (Newman et al. 2016).

Overall, more than half of Europeans believe that when it comes to decisions made about science and technology public dialogue is required (55%). Most think their government is doing too little to stimulate young people's interest in science (65%). Most agree that science has a positive impact on society (77%), and the majority of respondents in each country think this way. However, Europeans are concerned about the speed of change science and technology have, and their potential for negative consequences: 62% think science makes their way of life change too quickly.

Figure 5 Level of information and level of interest regarding science and technology in Europe. Source: European Commission (2013). © European Commission.

3.2 Promoting gender dimensions through innovative dissemination

Despite progress achieved towards gender equality in research and innovation during the past few years, a range of gender differences and inequalities persist (European Commission 2016, Elsevier 2017). For example, women continue to be underrepresented in science and technology, and research in general. This imbalance is also reflected in dissemination. In a large-scale study of more than 5.4 million research papers with more than 27 million authorships (Larivière et al. 2013), the authors

found that women represent fewer than 30% of authorships. This is a worldwide phenomenon, as men dominate authorship in all but a few countries. When it comes to first authorship, men are twice as likely to be first author as women.

There are indications from smaller-scale studies that this domination carries over to certain innovative dissemination channels. In a study of the aggregator of scientific blogs, ResearchBlogging.org, Shema et al. (2012) found that 72% of the 126 blogs analysed had only male authors. Mikki et al. (2015) investigated the digital presence of Norwegian scholars and found that women were underrepresented in a number of services such as ORCID and Google Scholar Profiles - with the exception were Academia.edu and ResearchGate, where the share of women was comparable to the share of male researchers in the sample.

Gender stereotyping is a topic that has mostly been studied in research on textbooks, but occasionally also in academic writing (see e.g. Martin 1991). Another gender-related topic regarding dissemination is the information-seeking behaviour of target audiences, which is studied particularly in medicine; examples are gender differences observed in patients (Carpenter et al. 2012) and general practitioners (Le 2016). For example, Carpenter et al. report that female patients with a rare illness were more likely to use the Internet as information source than their male counterparts.

Given these complex factors, OpenUP has identified four relevant gender aspects in context of our innovative dissemination case studies: (1) gender distribution within the team responsible for research and dissemination; (2) representation of gender, gender sensitivity and inclusiveness of the disseminated materials; (3) gender sensitivity and inclusiveness of the used dissemination tools, platforms and strategies; and (4) target audience, e.g. their gender distribution, and any relevant gender-sensitive aspects in their regard (e.g. when disseminating research results from medicine).

4. OpenUP activities and lessons learned

This section details the main findings from a series of distinct research and support activities undertaken regarding innovative dissemination – including work done to conduct primary research (OpenUP Pilots) in the area of innovative dissemination, map requirements for communicating to particular stakeholders, investigate the link between alternative metrics and innovative dissemination, and create training and support resources. Drawing these results together will enable cross-cutting conclusions to be drawn and inform the following section 5, which will then give practical guidance on innovative dissemination.

4.1 Innovative dissemination case studies

In 2016/17, OpenUP Task 4.1 conducted a range of compact case studies to gain an understanding of the effectiveness, suitability and impact of currently applied approaches. We here give an overview of these case studies, their purpose and the methods whereby they were collected. The full case studies are included as Appendix 1 of this report.

The cases were compiled via a landscape scan of existing research projects that used innovative dissemination methods and tools using internal project leads and a successful crowdsourcing strategy, whereby input was gathered via Twitter. In total, we collected 34 projects and 29 tools/methods. Project/dissemination type was assigned in a qualitative analysis, which revealed that citizen science/crowdsourcing was the most popular project type with 15 projects (see Figure 6). Next were public information/outreach projects (5 leads), projects focussing on education (4), and projects disseminating mostly within academia (4).

Figure 6. Distribution of types of research projects with innovative dissemination practices

From these leads we selected 10 cases, which we analysed in depth. The cases were selected as representative examples from the identified dissemination categories. In addition, we aimed for a distribution among disciplines and regions. As an additional criterion, our goal was to include projects that involve engagement and participation of target audiences (stages 2 and 3 in Beaufort's model, see section 2.1.2). 10 cases were selected and analysed along multiple dimensions including purpose, activities, tools and methods used, cost, levels of openness and gender representation in project participants and materials.

The 10 selected cases are summarised briefly here (see full case studies in Appendix 1):

- **Pluto Fly-By:** Science communication project to publicise NASA's New Horizons probe reaching Pluto in 2015 to a broad general audience. The spacecraft completed a nearly-decade-long journey to fly by Pluto, and revealed humanity's first close-up look at the distant dwarf planet (Dwarf planet). The goal of the dissemination was to communicate results of the mission and facts about Pluto to the broader audience. A well-resourced project, Pluto Fly-By employed a range of dissemination platforms (Twitter campaign, live streams, YouTube videos and press) to disseminate text, video, data, software and simulations.
- **Galaxy Zoo:** A well-known online citizen science project available on the platform Zooniverse.org that invites people to assist in the morphological classification of large numbers of galaxies through a website. Citizens classifying galaxies help scientists to understand how galaxies evolved over time and test theories about the nature of the Universe. The Galaxy Zoo website is the primary source of dissemination of the project activities. It includes a blog and a forum that support the volunteers in the discussion, analysis and classification of galaxies. Other dissemination activities are videos available on YouTube, releases and news articles in important journals and TV. The main dissemination contents are images, video, text and data.
- **Polymath Project:** Polymath projects, also known as massively collaborative online mathematics, represents a form of open Internet collaboration aimed towards a major mathematical goal, usually to solve yet unsolved mathematical problems. The aim was to target mathematicians that are motivated to bring new ideas and exchange them with others in order to solve difficult math problems, but also academics, teachers, students and other individuals interested in maths. Dissemination was conducted in terms of text and video through public information blogs, project home page, wiki pages, the Q&A site MathOverflow and YouTube videos.
- **Human Brain Project:** The article "Brain Projects Think Big" was published October 13, 2013, aiming to provide a younger audience (8-15) with an understanding of the Human Brain Project, via the Frontiers for Young Minds – Understanding Neuroscience journal. Publishing a child friendly version of the Human Brain Project on the Frontiers for Young Minds platform was an innovative approach to reach a different audience.
- **Gut (Giulia Enders):** The Gut project is a one-person project founded by Giulia Enders, with the aim to explain the functionality of a very complex organ, the gut, in a basic language that is understandable for the general audience. After her success in several science slams in 2012, Enders got an offer to write a book which was published to great popular success in March 2014, with Enders' accessible and humorous style engaging a wide audience.
- **Project SOHA:** The project "Open Science in Haiti and Francophone Africa (SOHA)" consists of action research, entitled "Open science as a collective tool for development of the power to act and of cognitive justice in Haiti and Francophone Africa: towards a roadmap". The objective is to understand the obstacles to the emergence of an open science culture in Francophone Africa and Haiti while creating a favourable environment to achieve the goal of an open science culture. Dissemination consists of several different activities ranging from YouTube videos, newsletters, and scientific events to online training courses, interviews and surveys. The dissemination objects are texts, data and video. The outputs are a network of emerging science shops, a dedicated blog, scientific publications and datasets. However the most important achievement is the consolidation of an international academic community, students, male and female researchers around the concept of cognitive justice.
- **Science at Home:** ScienceAtHome is an online platform for collaborative volunteer research, where people are invited to play scientific games, have fun and contribute to real discoveries on quantum physics, and human thinking. The team behind the project consists of scientists, game developers, designers and visual artists based at Aarhus University of Denmark and creates scientific games, with the aim to revolutionise scientific research and teaching by gameplay. The goal of the dissemination is to engage citizens to the project objectives, hence to create a community around the games developed, to maximise the input of results gathered from users' gameplay.

- **Transcribe Bentham:** An online collaborative initiative to transcribe the manuscripts of British philosopher Jeremy Bentham (1748 – 1832) from the archives of University College London. The goal of the Transcribe Bentham project was to start with the dissemination in very early stages of the project, right after the first research life-cycle phase - Design, because the transcription through crowdsourcing was identified as very crucial for the success of the project. Innovative and active dissemination ensured many volunteers contributed to the success of the project by transcribing handwritten and unpublished work of Bentham. One of most important outputs of the project are the digitised/transcribed Bentham manuscripts that are made publicly available.
- **Homer Multitext Project:** The Homer Multitext (HMT) is a long-term project seeking to present the Homeric Iliad and Odyssey in a critical framework. HMT invites fellow researchers from all over the world to collaborate in the form of diplomatic editions, images of historical documents, and translations. The project emphasizes collaborative research, openly licensed data, and innovative uses of technology. All material is openly licensed. The project had various dissemination outputs. Next to the blog the project published a number of scientific publications, images of scanned manuscripts and transcripts, and a complete edition of the Venetus A manuscript, which is openly available as PDF. The disseminated materials include text, photos, a book (the aforementioned PDF), and the HMT software. Media formats include documentation, blog posts, data/transcripts and textual variances, as well as images/scans of manuscripts and source code. The source code and resources on GitHub are being regularly updated.
- **Innovations in Scholarly Communications:** 101 Innovations in scholarly communication is a project that aims to analyse in detail research life-cycle phases and innovative tools that are used by researchers in each of the phases. Specifically, the purpose of the project was to investigate to what extent researchers are using the innovative communication tools compared to traditional ones and what impact these tools have on the research workflow. Dissemination activities range from the distribution of the tools database in Google Spreadsheets, the global survey (i.e., was open from May 10, 2015 until February 10, 2016), interactive visualizations of survey results, collaboration with 108 partners (using their communication channels and mailing lists) to public blogs, social media, talks, webcasts and podcasts. One of the most interesting outputs is a snapshot of 101 tools visualized in a circle aligned to six research-lifecycle phases. To the dissemination outputs count also datasets and scripts as well as open peer reviewed scientific article and poster.

4.2 Experiments with innovative dissemination in various contexts

The aim of the OpenUP pilot studies, which were conducted within WP6, was to test and/or evaluate selected innovative peer review, dissemination, and impact measuring approaches applied to specific research areas and communities. To achieve this, the OpenUP team involved and committed interested and engaged research communities from arts & humanities, social sciences, energy, and life sciences. Together with these communities, the OpenUP team applied and tested technical and processual solutions identified during research activities for WP4. Specific stakeholder requirements as well as specificities of the particular dissemination settings were addressed as well. Three of the seven pilots had direct relevance for innovative dissemination, one (Pilot 3) on data publishing and two (Pilots 4 and 5) on reaching out to stakeholders beyond traditional research audiences. Details of the three pilots are summarised in the table below. Following this, the main findings are reported. The full Final Evaluations Reports for each pilot are included as Appendix 2 at the end of this document.

Table 2 Involved communities in the OpenUP pilot studies and estimated impact

OpenUP Pilot Study	Involved Community	Numbers of organisations and individuals involved	Estimated Impact
Pilot 3: A data journal	DARIAH	2 contact persons in	Short-term:

for the Arts and Humanities		DARIAH-EU and DARIAH-DE 20 workshop participants (2 workshops)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> contributing to the ongoing discussion on data sharing in the Humanities Long-term: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> implementation of results in the development of a data journal using the infrastructure within DARIAH
Pilot 4: Transferring the research lifecycle to the web (Open Science Repositories)	Citizen scientists, Members of Zooniverse Students Developers	3 organizations 20+ individuals so far Estimated for live test: 100+ individuals	Short-term: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> User experience Long-term: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Empowerment of citizens: access to an easy to use collaboration tool
Pilot 5: Addressing & reaching businesses and the public with research output	SmarterTogether project (from December 2016 - December 2017) ReFlex project (from March - July 2018)	3 organisations 6 individuals	Short-term: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Guidelines applied by Researchers & Project communication staff Long-term: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Guidelines picked up and extended by communities through OpenUP Hub

4.2.1 Pilot 3: A data journal for the Arts and Humanities

The pilot has a dual purpose: on the one hand, it describes the data sharing practices within Humanities research, and on the other hand, the study evaluates how quality assessment and (open) peer review can be applied to research data within this field of study. Based on existing e-Infrastructures and practices of Humanities research groups the pilot analyses and demonstrates the feasibility of a basic workflow that will combine the publication of data with commenting and reviewing systems. The research setting is provided by DARIAH-EU and DARIAH-DE, their extended network of Humanities research groups and by the research groups related to the Campus Labor at the University of Göttingen. Based upon this work, the following lessons were learned:

- Diversity of research data:** Research data is as diverse as the disciplines that use them. In the on-going European discourse around open data, prevailing definitions and understandings of data relate to measurable, collected, reported, and analysed data. This is not a common concept in the Humanities, where content and research cannot be related to numbers and statistics. To address research communities in the Humanities, an adapted definition of data is needed. We suggest defining research data in the Humanities as the evidence used to inform or support research conclusions.
- Principles of research data management and data journals in the Humanities:** Due to the varied fields of study involved in the Humanities, contextualization of data is needed to understand research data management. A data journal usually provides templates for data description and offers researchers guidance on where to deposit and how to describe and present their data. A data journal framework should include assignment of persistent identifiers (PIDs) to datasets, peer review of data, metadata information and technical check, links to related outputs (journal articles), facilitation of data citation, standards compliance, and discoverability (indexing of the data).
- Fostering data publication and quality assessment: Principles for creating an Open Research Database:** As the HMD use case shows, Social Sciences data users appreciate that the platform makes source data available, provides transparent data processing procedures, detailed documentation, and that it is trustworthy. These are also important features for any other research data service or platform. Guiding principles for creating this open research data

platform were comparability, flexibility, accessibility and reproducibility. These principles are applicable to other research areas as well.

- **Motivations for sharing research data in Social Sciences and the Humanities:** A campus-wide survey conducted in 2015 at the University of Lille suggests that students in Social Sciences the Humanities are more interested in achieving impact and visibility (international repository) and disciplinary specificity (laboratory) rather than in creating a multidisciplinary, national or institutional solution.
- **Barriers to open research data (focus: Humanities and Life Sciences/Biomedicine):** Pilot 3 showed that one of the main obstacles of data sharing in the Humanities is the generally closed world of scientific discourse. The dispersed research communities often fail to connect to one another because of the language barriers. Humanities scholars very often publish in their national languages, and the trend is to continue doing so in the future. Europe lacks an integrated database of published journals in various national languages. A database of this kind could be a sort of 'who's who' within a particular field of research. There is a lack of information and oversight in the biomedical field. This is due to missing infrastructures as well as heterogeneous and non-standardized publication practices regarding the provision of open data. Even if there are guidelines such as FAIR data, useful criteria for “good data” which account for the heterogeneity of research fields such as biomedicine are still missing. To bring this to success we need to consider field specific solutions or standards. Another reason is the lack of training and technical expertise for opening and curating the data. Similarly, a lack of standards and common guidelines in data management has been observed in the Humanities (Pilot 3). Due to this, it is very difficult to connect data (Humanities). Lack of standardized workflows for data curation, sharing and publishing is, in fact, a barrier in many disciplines.

4.2.2 Pilot 4: Transferring the research lifecycle to the web (Open Online Research)

In this pilot, we addressed the question whether data analysis and data collection in qualitative research can be transferred to open online groups, in which potentially both academics and non-academics can participate. A special focus lied on mechanisms to reach out to and engage citizens in qualitative research processes. Our aim was to transfer the data-analysis and data collection parts of the research lifecycle to the web. To this end, we developed dedicated software called OpenOnlineResearch (OOR)³ further. In Pilot 4 we successfully tested and further developed OOR. In particular, we tested the applicability of this online solution to involve citizens in qualitative research. The goal was to gain further insight into working practices and address current challenges/gaps of open online collaboration approaches applied to qualitative research.

The results of the test rounds done in context of Pilot 4 confirmed that online applications such as the OpenOnlineResearch (OOR) tool can enable citizens to gather and analyse data online and openly. By means of a model investing in social moderation, we demonstrated that open online interpretation of qualitative data is feasible and that yet unused parts of the research cycle can be opened to wider ranges of collaborators both within and outside academia.

We learned that a simple tool such as OOR works without the need for having detailed instructions for the functionalities of the tool. Input of scientists, however, is essential for the formulation of sound research questions and instructions. Online collaboration needs moderation (either technically or by humans) to settle differences. However, we found that conflicts were rare and that participants were willing to collaborate in most cases.

³ Login <http://mooruva.staging.vellance.net/> (htaccess): User: openup, Pass: CzTd4xjrGuuawbp92tGntKh

4.2.3 Pilot 5: Addressing & reaching businesses and the public with research output

The goal of the fifth OpenUP pilot study was to analyse and test how disseminated research results can be made more interesting, appealing, and usable for target audiences beyond the research community. In this pilot we particularly addressed dissemination to **businesses** and the **general public**. In context of WP4 Task 4.4 we interviewed 7 science communication experts (4 male, 3 female) to define requirements and expectations by these targeted audiences. In addition, we consulted one of the community contacts of the previously involved SmarterTogether⁴ project, who was responsible for project communication. Based upon the feedback gathered, we created guidelines and recommendations for researchers who want to communicate their research to target audiences beyond academia. The resulting recommendations are included in the following subsection of this report.

A major methodological finding, however, is that a diverse approach for defining and supporting open science dissemination is needed. There is no one size fits all. We came up with guidelines to support communication to two large target groups: businesses and the general public. The test run done in context of Pilot 5 showed that the guidelines were very useful for improving the dissemination strategy of the project. However, the division in the two above mentioned target groups has proven not to be necessarily evident or useful for all projects. The division into these two main target groups is rather arbitrary and cannot necessarily be applied to other specific target groups. A more diverse approach to defining and supporting open science dissemination is needed (e.g. including other target groups or addressing trans-disciplinary questions). The guidelines that we authored already provide good guidance; however only for planning a dissemination strategy tailored to these two target audiences, and not beyond. For future research it would be relevant to explore other ways to structure the guidelines and their content to provide additional guidance for the points that our guidelines fail to provide substantial support.

4.3 Recommendations for reaching businesses and general public as target audiences

In this section we summarise recommendations for communicating research to businesses and the general public as target audiences. The following paragraphs summarise results from communication expert interviews, in particular needs and requirements by the two target groups. The results are reported in more detail in a previous deliverable⁵.

4.3.1 Stakeholder analysis of businesses

In general, businesses want to stay up to date about what is going on in research projects and not miss latest developments that are relevant for their own developments, services and products. This is particularly true for businesses without their own R&D department. Business audiences are not that much interested in getting to know comprehensive technical details; they want to know what the main output is, how it can help the company and how they can apply it.

Businesses are also interested in finding new R&D cooperation partners, e.g. to outsource R&D activities, share resources, or validate research done in-house. In this context having strong IPRs is very important for businesses.

In some areas, e.g. in health society or public technology, businesses need input from independent research providing independent data confirming that their products are safe, have an effect, or an

⁴ <https://www.smartertogether.at/>

⁵ Vignoli, M. (2017). D6.2 Interim Use Case Evaluation Report. 30.11.2017. http://openup-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/01/OpenUP_D6.2_Interim-Use-Case-Evaluation-Report.pdf

overall positive risk-benefit balance. Examples are public debates with environmental organisations or the general public.

The need by businesses to receive information from some research areas (e.g. arts and humanities, social sciences) might not seem evident. In these areas, there is a bigger discrepancy between science and businesses.

In commissioned consulting, businesses expect the researchers to deliver a clear and quick answer to a problem. They are not looking for possible solutions and their caveats; they want clear answers that help them solving problems that they encounter in practice.

Depending on the research area, information required from research varies. For example, in the manufacturing industry information is needed to reduce costs, make products more attractive, and to maintain/achieve the pole position on market.

On the one hand, industry is interested in using the results from research. For them it is essential to know how to access the results, under which licenses, and if they are openly available. It is important for them to know which IPRs apply and which of the results can be reused. This information should be well understandable. On the other hand, businesses do not only need research outputs such as concrete results, papers, patents. They are interested in updates on any latest research development. This can include everything up to messages or short reports on what you are up to right now.

Businesses also need people. They want to know principle investigators in their own sectors to be able to collaborate. Not only do they want to know about events that researchers are attending. They are also looking for individual experts in the field and their expertise. Businesses are always looking for opportunities to get to know researchers and find possible collaboration opportunities.

4.3.2 Key messages and communication formats for reaching businesses

- Before defining key messages and communication formats it is essential to define who the specific audience is, e.g. pharma industry, telecom manufacturers, etc. The more specific the better.
- When you define your communication plan, define a timeframe and milestones for identifying the audience and start disseminating to them. Make sure to appoint persons responsible for these tasks.
- Align research communication and key messages with what the targeted businesses do. Transform the message to fit the targeted businesses' requirements and expectations.
- Explain what you are doing and get the key message to your audience. Start with the knowledge base that they already have by involving their world in the story. As a result, the message will be easier to understand, and it gets a personal touch.
- Be open to discussions, and have a platform for businesses to enable a two-way communication.
- The specifications of the requested research reports are set and communicated by the company (particularly in commissioned research settings). In these cases, the company should receive the information in exactly the format requested. Businesses will have trained staff who can deal with scientific information.
- Clarify the IPR beforehand: make sure that relevant and sensitive results are only available for the company.
- There is no format fitting all sectors and businesses. Choose formats suitable for presenting to and discussing with target audiences from the targeted sector in a two-way communication.
- It is recommendable not to go just with one format. Use 3-4 main formats that your target audience uses.

- Think multi-channel and multi-format. Do not put all energy in one big campaign. Use various tools, e.g. video, social media strategy, marketing actions, paid media, price relations, public relations (influential bloggers).
- Communication material should be in the language that your target audience understands best. To achieve a broad dissemination, in particular for EU projects, use English as dissemination language. For national projects use the national language; but always provide an executive summary in English.
- Directly involve your target groups in face-to-face events or meetings (e.g. special workshops for industry partners organised in context of research projects).
- Educate your target business by inviting them to talks and conferences where the research is being showcased.
- Advertise and disseminate these events via social media channels (e.g. Twitter, LinkedIn). ResearchGate is not recommended as this network is mostly used to reach peers from research. Please consult also the new H2020 Social Media Guide for EU funded R&I projects (European Commission 2018).

4.3.3 Stakeholder analysis of the general public

The general public is a very large and heterogeneous group, and without having a specific subgroup in mind it is difficult to pinpoint their interest. In many cases, the general public is not actively looking for specific information from research. However, citizens are generally interested in understanding how science is trying to solve current or upcoming challenges.

The general public is interested in a lot of science contents; it does not matter if it is cancer research, chemistry, biology etc. What is important is that they can get something away from the story, and that they gained some knowledge in this process. They are interested in science e.g. due to personal reasons, a pure interest to learn new knowledge, or because they have a particular problem that they want to solve.

Some stakeholders from the general public (e.g. patients) have a major interest to talk to the experts and to get actively involved in research - either due to their personal situation or their enthusiasm or passion for science. Be aware that if you highlight researchers in your communication strategy, individual citizens or patient organisations might contact them directly.

Everything that is being researched will find interest somewhere at the general public. However, it should be disseminated in an appropriate format. The general public is interested in information that has a direct connection to whatever is on their mind at the moment. There are moments in which citizens are interested in something specific, e.g. if they need to decide on a treatment or to deal with pollution in their garden. But when they are looking for input and evidence it is really hard for them to find. There is a disconnection between research information providers and receivers: there are a lot of flashpoints and need to understanding research information. However, when citizens are in need for this information, it is often not provided on the channels that they are looking at. If the research community becomes more open to discuss and actively participate in public debates, it would be easier for the general public to find research information.

Some citizens are also interested in finding expert contact persons. For instance, in the health research area individual citizens might contact researchers who are declared as contact persons for specific research projects or areas.

4.3.4 Key messages and communication formats for reaching the general public

- Before defining key messages and communication formats it is essential to define who is your target audience. Identify a specific group that might be interested in your research, e.g. children, adults, students, senior citizens, parents.

- When you define your communication plan, define a timeframe and milestones for identifying the audience and start disseminating to them. Make sure to appoint persons responsible for these tasks.
- Explain research outcomes through the big picture. The communication format should not be too technical and it should tell a story. By following a storyline, complex topics can be more easily communicated to citizens. Attach the topic to a sensational detail to draw interest and to engage your audience. Write so that everyone can understand rather than to sound smart (Leeming 2016).
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- Explain what research does to improve their life and relate it to their everyday life.
- There is communication format fitting all general public target audiences. Flexibility is the key, and the format to be chosen depends on your dissemination objectives.
- There are many possibilities, e.g. organising a big communication campaign; targeting a very specific target group (e.g. patients); or provide plain information that people are waiting for.
- It is recommendable to go with the social media trend and use, next to text, visual online resources (e.g. videos, animations). The latter are more appealing and easy to share. Using social media such as Facebook, LinkedIn, or Twitter helps gaining some visibility. Please consult also the new H2020 Social Media Guide for EU funded R&I projects (European Commission 2018).
- It is recommendable to not only provide information, but to stimulate a dialogue with your general public target audience. This needs creativity and flexibility. Think about applying Citizen Science approaches.
- Organise or participate in events targeting general public audiences (e.g. EU researchers' nights targeting school or high-school children as well as adults).

4.3.5 Conclusions and recommendations: Defining the role of Open Science Communication Expert

In the light of the recent debate around “alternative facts” and “degraded public discourse” (Ferber 2018), immediate call to action to improve communication of research information to general public audiences becomes evident. Eagleman (2013), Libutti & Valente (2006), and already Callon (1999) made clear that communicating and interacting with the public is essential to improve perception and awareness of science. The growing need for improved and more interactive public communication of fact based science is accompanied by a substantial gap in the current science communication system. Science communication is divided between dissemination of research outcomes to peers, which is done by researchers (e.g. at conferences, in scientific publications); and popular, general public-targeted communication of research information, which is traditionally done by research journalists, communication departments or intermediaries. However, public communication of research cannot longer be carried out by professional general public and specialist media alone. Researchers need to increasingly become active and involved in public dissemination and debates instead of operating behind closed academic doors. In the 21st century science and media landscape social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter and YouTube play a crucial role to reach out for public audiences (Fingerle 2017). This requires science communication experts to adapt to these new media.

Reaching out to public target audiences requires specific skills for which researchers are traditionally not trained for. As we have made clear in this document, there is an increasing need to fill the gap between scientific, “complex” dissemination to an expert public and a more popular, “simplified” communication to public target audiences. Targeted and interactive Open Science Communication should be supported on policy and institutional level to increase active participation by researchers. In this context, additional funding of science communication activities, setting appropriate incentives and providing communication and soft-skills training for researchers are key factors.

To fill this gap, we propose to create new science communication roles and positions to be staffed with people both skilled in science communication and with science expert knowledge. Currently, research-

ers and science journalists do not necessarily have the necessary skills, and they can definitely not cover the additional effort coming with Open Science Communication activities on top of their current tasks. It is important to have, next to Public Relations and marketing staff, trained experts with the necessary scientific background and skills, who are also trained in communicating to and interacting with audiences outside the research community by means of Web 2.0 technologies. Policy makers and strategic HR should see this as a chance to create new jobs for the growing number of qualified young researchers, who currently only have poor access to the job market in research and academia.

4.4 Alternative Metrics enable the adoption of innovative dissemination

OpenUP Deliverable D5.4 “Report on linking channels of dissemination and Altmetrics”⁶ established that one of the reasons why new practices have not been taken up are deeply entrenched reward systems which are linked to contemporary regimes of evaluation. The report noted uncertainty as to whether a new regime of evaluation is emerging. However, a major conclusion must be that enabling reward for innovative dissemination activities will require adequate measurement of usage via those channels. The report defines a taxonomy of dissemination channels that can be used as data-sources for alternative metrics. This taxonomy covers different aspects that are relevant for how these channels can be interpreted. In the following, we provide a list of tables that covers different groups of services and thus dissemination linking them with relevant information about how they are appreciated and valued both within and across a specific field. By so doing, we aim to provide orientation for scholars who plan to develop a dissemination strategy and are unsure about how what might be relevant in this respect and how a certain choice of communication is appreciated within their community. Each table, e.g. each group of services – covers the following aspects:

Attention: Information about the extent to which channels of dissemination have the potential to increase attention for different types scientific output (scaled from low to high potential).

General scholarly appreciation: How a specific communication channel is appreciated across various scholarly audiences (scaled from low to high appreciation).

Scholarly relevance: Information as to whether a specific channel of communication is of importance for either supporting scholarly workflows or is considered to be useful for addressing specific audiences with scholarly information (indicated as yes for relevant, no for not relevant).

Field specific appreciation: Information as to whether the appreciation of a specific communication channel is field specific or not (indicated as yes for field specific, no for not field specific).

Metrics: Information about what data can be used to provide alternative metrics for a specific channel (e.g., citations, downloads, views).

Provider coverage: Information about which channel of communication is tracked by which provider of altmetrics data.

Technical Accessibility: Information about whether a specific communication channel can be freely accessed through its users or by third party persons.

⁶ http://openup-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/01/OpenUP_D5.4-Report-on-final-taxonomy-linking-channels-of-dissemination-and-altmetrics-indicators.pdf

Intergenerational assessment: Information from OpenUP survey data about generational differences in appreciation and usage of specific communication channels (scaled from low to high generational differences).

4.4.1 Doing Science and science made public

The services which are grouped together in this dimension can be perceived as communication channels in the narrower sense, that is, their focus is primarily on communicating results or establishing attention for scholarly results. However, most of them (e.g. twitter or Facebook) have not been designed specifically for scholarly usage, but have simply become more common among scholars. On the other hand, specific services have established that imitated the structure of such services but have been developed responding to scholarly needs. Potentially, however, all of these channels can be considered as communication channels of scholars. Here researchers wishing research to have general scholarly appreciation via channel relevant to their field should use consider blogging and ResearchGate, for instance.

Table 3: Doing Science and science made public

Dimension: Doing Science and Science made public	Service 1 Blogging	Service 2 twitter	Service 3 Facebook	Service 4 Re-searchGate
Attention (expert interviews, desk research)	Medium	High	High	Medium
General scholarly appreciation (Survey data)	Medium	Low	Very low	Medium
Scholarly relevance (literature review, expert interviews)	Yes	No	No	Yes
Field specific appreciation (expert interviews)	Yes	No	No	Yes
Metrics (desk research)	Citations Downloads Views	Mentions Followers	Mentions Views Likes	Activities within the network
Provider coverage (desk research)	Altmetric, Plum	Altmetric, Plum, PloS, Impactstory	Altmetric., Plum	None
Technical Accessibility (API)	Partly	Yes (but restricted)	Yes (but restricted)	No
Intergenerational differences in assessment (survey)	High	Medium	Low	NA

4.4.2 Explaining and Entertaining

In the second group of services, explaining and entertaining, communication channels provide not only textual, but also visual, audio or audiovisual means to communicate research. The structure of contributions in these channels is different to traditional types of output. But they increasingly gain attention. The most visible and dominant source in this category is YouTube which hosts a lot of channels for scholarly topics that have many followers. YouTube is the only one which is consistently tracked and integrated in measures among the different altmetric data services. As can be seen, there are fewer reasons to prefer Vimeo or Pinterest from a communication point of view.

Table 4: Explaining and Entertaining

Dimension: Explaining and Entertaining	Service 1 Youtube	Service 2 Vimeo	Service 3 Pinterest
Attention (expert interviews, desk research)	High	Medium	Low
General scholarly appreciation (Survey data)	Medium	Low	Very low

Scholarly relevance (literature review, expert interviews)	Yes	No	No
Field specific appreciation (expert interviews)	Yes	No	No
Metrics (desk research)	Followers Mentions Views	Followers Mentions	Mentions Views Likes
Provider coverage (desk research)	Altmetric, Plum	Altmetric, Plum	Altmetric., Plum
Technical Accessibility (API)	Yes	No	Yes (but restricted)
Intergenerational assessment (survey)	Medium	Low	Low

4.4.3 Empowering reproducibility

The dimension ‘Empowering reproducibility’ groups various services that aim at enabling sharing of data or code. Reproducibility is a core aim of Open Science, supported by innovative dissemination to the extent that new research objects (data, code, protocols) are made available in new, standardised ways. Comparable to the first dimension, this group consists of services that are specifically designed for scholarly demands (Figshare) and others that address more diverse audiences (Github). Figshare (as part of digital science) can be considered as the one that is most specifically oriented towards scholarly audiences. Nevertheless, the services in this category are particularly used and appreciated by engineers and computer scientists who have developed a certain culture of sharing and collaborative knowledge production as our expert interviewees suggest. These kinds of tools are also appreciated by Open Science activists as they document engagement in providing transparent access to how data were collected and algorithms were constructed. Nevertheless, the appreciation of these channels is rather low. However, publishers aim at promoting these services and encourage their authors to provide data or resources relevant for understanding how research was conducted.

Table 5: Empowering reproducibility

Dimension: Empowering reproducibility	Service 1 Github	Service 2 Figshare
Attention (expert interviews, desk research)	Low	Low
General scholarly appreciation (Survey data)	Low	Low
Scholarly relevance (literature review, expert interviews)	Some	Some
Field specific appreciation (expert interviews)	Yes	Yes
Metrics (desk research)	Shares	Shares
Provider coverage (desk research)	Altmetric, Plum, PloS	Altmetric, Plum
Technical Accessibility (API)	Yes	Yes
Intergenerational assessment (survey)	Low	Low

4.5 Training and Awareness Building

Figure 7. Innovative Dissemination Workshop, Graz, June 2018

OpenUP has undertaken a range of training and awareness building activities including short-form workshops at the Open Science conference 2017 in Berlin and Open Science Fair 2017 in Athens, presentations at events like OpenCon London 2017, Open Access Tage 2018 in Graz and LIBER 2018 in Lille. In addition, a major full-day training workshop on “Increasing Visibility and Impact through Innovative Dissemination” was held on 20th June 2018 in Graz, Austria, in collaboration with Graz University of Technology and the University of Graz. The workshop was open to early career researchers and doctoral students of all institutions. Through expert presentations and interactive breakout sessions, participants learned more about how to increase the impact of their research via novel tools and methods, including how to reach the media, industry, policymakers, and wider society. The interactive programme included talks and interactive breakout sessions from invited speakers (Bianca Kramer, Jon Tennant and Peter Kraker) and OpenUP experts (Michela Vignoli and Tony Ross-Hellauer). Members of the Graz University of Technology and University of Graz teams for publications services and public relations were also on hand to share their knowledge and learn more about how they could help their researchers. The workshop was highly successful in motivating participants to take up new platforms and processes. The workshop report is included here as Appendix 3 and available online via the OpenUP Hub,⁷ to serve as a model programme for future such events.

⁷<https://www.openuphub.eu/community/blog/item/report-on-openup-innovative-dissemination-training-workshop-20th-june-2018-graz>

5. Practical guidance for researchers and other stakeholders

The following ten steps to innovative dissemination described in this section represents the synthesis of the foregoing multidimensional research activities. They are based on findings and conclusions derived via various instruments: literature review, survey, case studies, innovative dissemination research pilots, stakeholder engagement via various channels, validation workshops and presentations/poster presentations at various events. The goal of the framework is to provide stakeholders (primarily researchers, but also intermediaries) with an entry point to innovative dissemination, so that they can choose methods and tools based on their audience, their skills and their requirements. Given this scope, this section differs stylistically from the others, addressing the reader in the second person.

5.1 Step 1: Get the basics right

Despite changes in communication technologies and models, there are some basic aspects of dissemination that remain important: to define objectives, map audience(s), target messages and create a dissemination plan.

5.1.1 Define objectives

The motivation to disseminate research can come in many forms. You might want to share your findings, to raise awareness of issues, or invite audience engagement. Start by asking what you want to achieve with your dissemination. To assist, the below table categorises various possible motivations: sharing, informing, interacting, engaging, support and funding, and personal/organisational goals.

Table 7. Researchers' objectives with regards to innovative dissemination

Category	Objective
(1) Sharing	(1a) Contributing to the body of knowledge
	(1b) Enabling others to build on top of one's research
(2) Informing	(2a) Informing target audiences
	(2b) Raising awareness of the findings
(3) Interacting	(3a) Receiving feedback on research
	(3b) Stimulating discussions and public understanding of science
(4) Engaging	(4a) To transfer research to practice
	(4b) Influencing policymaking and practice
	(4c) Participation of target audiences
	(4d) Collaboration with target audiences
(5) Support/Funding	(5a) Maintaining public support for research
	(5b) Justifying funding of research
	(5c) Attracting future funding
	(5d) Satisfying contractual obligations (e.g. research funding)
(6) Personal/ organisational goals	(6a) Raising one's own or one's organisation's profile
	(6b) Provide personal enjoyment/reward

5.1.2 Map your audience

Reflecting on the purpose of your dissemination activities will enable you to begin to map your audience. Think about who exactly you are trying to reach with your research results and for which purposes. Who is most affected by your research? Who might find it valuable? Get to know your target audiences, their needs and expectations of the research outcomes, as well as their preferred communi-

cation channels. Specifying the types of audiences you want to reach as much as possible will help you develop a detailed understanding of their interests and align your messages and media with their needs and priorities. Whether you want to share, inform, or interact, reflecting on the potential audiences will then allow you to further refine your communication objectives by linking them to target audiences.

In the course of our exploration, we have identified various stakeholders of research dissemination. The stakeholders can take various roles in the dissemination process:

- **Initiators:** Entities which initiate the dissemination process.
- **Intermediaries:** Entities which support or mediate the dissemination process.
- **Target audiences:** Targeted recipients of the dissemination process.
- **Management:** Entities which are very keen on research being disseminated and try to guide and stimulate dissemination.

It should be noted that these roles are not clear-cut. Publishers or funders may initiate dissemination, as may citizen scientists, for example.

<p>1) Initiators</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Researchers b) Research projects c) Research organisations 	<p>2) Intermediaries</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Publishers b) Librarians c) Journalists d) Science communicators e) Service providers 	<p>3) Target audiences</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Researchers b) Teachers c) Students d) Schoolchildren e) Policy makers/ government f) Practitioners g) Journalists h) Industry/business i) Charities/NGOs j) Citizen scientists k) General public
<p>4) Management</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Research organisations b) Funders 		

Figure 8. Stakeholders of innovative dissemination, categorized according to their main role

5.1.3 Target/frame your messages

How will these messages reach your audiences, and what auxiliary knowledge will they need in order to best take it up? What will these audiences need to understand your research and make decisions based on it? Once you know your target group, it is essential to target and frame the key messages that you want to communicate. In general, it is important to make sure that the key messages and information that you provide is relevant for the targeted audience. Always think of what they want to hear from you, not what you want to tell them.

Choosing media and format of your communication strongly depends on your communication objectives, i.e. what you want to achieve. There are many ways to communicate your research, e.g. direct messages, blog post, tweeting about it or putting your research on Instagram. Think about who you are trying to reach, what message you want to communicate, and what your audience should be able to do with it. Form and content go hand in hand. Which intermediaries can you engage in amplifying your messages? You can share your key message to reach your target audience as passive listeners. However, you can also activate your target audiences and enable them to become active or do something with the content that you provide. Social media and other platforms offer various possibilities not to only passively share your messages, but also to actively involve your target audiences.

5.1.4 Create a dissemination plan

Once these steps are complete, bring this together into a dissemination plan that will help you throughout the research process. The dissemination plan should summarize aims and type of stakeholders to be addressed as well as the milestones of the research life cycle in which you may have some intermediate, meaningful results to communicate. This is a first, important draft that outlines activities to be planned, resources and timelines, that has to be periodically updated and adapted according to the results obtained so far and/or possible changes of work context.

Plan both activities related to the communication/information about the project and those specifically focused on the re-use of your research results. The first involves engagement, addressing a wide audience to take interest in your research. For instance, an early announcement of the topics and aims of the project creates expectations and awareness able to build a network of “followers” taking advantage of social media and/or scientific events. Secondly, focusing on re-use aims to share project results with identified target audiences through appropriate channels and tools for specific purposes. For instance, identify in your plan well-known open access repositories to disseminate scientific articles, data, software etc. as well as events in which you can engage your identified stakeholders in an interactive discussion. In the dissemination of research results, always consider any funder requirements as well as the wishes of any partners establishing transparent behaviour rules and/or proposing appropriate licences.

Have a clear picture of possible constraints related to your project that may include resource, time and funds. In planning dissemination activities, distribute tasks and effort to ensure regular updates of content targeted to different communities. Engage those with special skills in the use and/or development of appropriate communication tools, to help you in using the right language and support you in finding the suitable occasions to reach your identified stakeholders.

5.2 Step 2: Encourage participation

In the age of Open Science, don't just broadcast, go for multi-directional dissemination. Invite & engage others to foster participation & collaboration. Scholarship is a collaborative activity, and so we should not expect research dissemination to be uni-directional, especially not in the digital age with our proliferation of social and communication platforms and tools. Dissemination is increasingly done at earlier stages of the research lifecycle and is thus becoming an integral part of the whole research workflow. In addition, dissemination becomes more interactive; as a result, it is often difficult to draw the line between the activities of dissemination and participation.

Innovative forms of research dissemination, which enable participation and collaboration of audiences within and beyond academia are increasingly common. Disseminating early and often showcases the progress of your work and demonstrates productivity and engagement. People like to see progress and positively react to narrative, so you can give regular updates to your followers and actively request their feedback engaging them in the research process. This can range from blogging or tweeting early research findings for early feedback, right to actively engaging citizen scientists in research projects, e.g. to collect data or analyse findings. Or, you can inform or educate them about the research

methods and results by addressing them through social media channels or streaming platforms (open science, open education). Be aware that while some may be very encouraging, others might be harshly critical, which could lead to challenging dialogues. In any case, active involvement of citizens and other target audiences beyond academia can help increase the societal impact of your research. Further, involving businesses early on can align research closely to industry requirements and expectations thus potentially increasing commercial impact.

5.3 Step 3: Open science for impact

Open Science is transparent and accessible knowledge that is shared and developed through collaborative networks (Vicente-Saez and Martinez-Fuentes, 2018). It encompasses a variety of practices, including areas like open access to publications, open research data, open source software/tools, open workflows, citizen science, open educational resources, and alternative methods for research evaluation including open peer review (Pontika et al. 2015). Open Science is rooted in principles of participation and transparency, enabling others to collaborate in, contribute to, scrutinise and re-use research and spread knowledge as widely as possible. As such, innovative dissemination is a core aim of Open Science.

Embracing Open Science principles can boost the impact of research. Firstly, Open Access publications seem to accrue more citations than their closed counterparts (Tennant et al., 2016). A comprehensive bibliography of studies documenting the impact of Open Access on citations is available from SPARC Europe since 2013 (sparceurope.org/oaca/).

Disseminating publications as preprints (Bourne et al., 2017) in advance of or parallel to journal submission can increase impact. Very often, traditional publishing takes a long time, with the waiting time between submission and acceptance of a paper being around 100 days (Powell, 2016). Preprinting hence speeds dissemination meaning that findings are available sooner.

Dissemination of other Open Science outputs which would usually remain hidden also not only ensures the transparency and reproducibility of research (Munafò et al., 2017), but also means that more research elements are released which can potentially impact upon others. Making FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable) research data and code available enables re-use, and hence further citations (Pasquetto et al., 2017). Publishing research proposals, protocols and open notebooks act as advertisements for ongoing research and enable others to re-use methods.

To enable re-use, embrace open licenses. When it comes to innovative dissemination, the goal is usually that the materials are accessible to as large an audience as possible. If open licenses are not used, while they may be free to access, they cannot be used, modified or shared. Best is CC BY or CC O. Some projects make their results re-usable for non-commercial purposes only. This limitation, however, prevents the use of materials in many forms of (open) educational resources and other open projects, including Wikipedia.

5.4 Step 4: Remix traditional outputs

Give traditional outputs like research articles and books an impact-boost with accompanying lay-summaries, press-releases, blogs, and visual/video abstracts.

Traditional research outputs are not irreconcilable with innovative dissemination. Research outputs like scientific articles and books can gain an impact-boost through accompanying lay-summaries, press-releases, blogs, and visual/video abstracts. Considering media coverage in general there are countless media resources interested in science-related stories. Free media coverage can be an easy way to get results out to as many people as possible. Most universities and large research organization have an office for public affairs or communication: liaise with these experts to disseminate research

findings widely through public media. Press releases offer one of the most effective ways to disseminate information to the media. Consider writing a press release for manuscripts that have been accepted for publication in journals or books and use sample forms and tools available online to assist you in the process.

Another useful tool to disseminate traditional research outputs is to release a research summary document. This one- or two-page document that clearly and concisely summarizes the key conclusions from every research initiative. It can combine several studies by the same investigator or by a research group and need to integrate two main components: key findings and fact sheets (preferably with graphical images to illustrate your point). This can be published on your institutional website as well on research blogs, thematic hubs or simply posted on your social media profiles. If your data visualization is too technical and not easily understandable by a non-expert reader consider creating ad hoc image for this document. Use online tool to upload a sample of your data and develop smart graph and infographs: [Infogr.am](#), [Datawrapper](#), [Easil.ly](#), [Pick To Chart](#), [Venngage](#), [Visually](#). Your research summary could be easily shared via social media if you are using it. If you are not using it or you are not so active - keeping up with social media may become a full-time job – consider focusing your effort on one or two tools to achieve a bigger impact in the public domain.

To maximise the impact of your conference presentations or posters, there are several steps that can be taken. For instance, you can upload your slides to a repository and add a DOI to your presentation, schedule tweets before and during the conference that use the conference hashtag to publicise your talk or poster, and add information about your contribution to email out-of-office messages (Teperek, 2018).

5.5 Step 5: Keep the right profile

Whether the initiator is an individual researcher, a research project or a research organization, establishing a prominent and unique identity online and offline are essential for communicating. Use personal websites, social media accounts, researcher identifiers and academic social networks to make you and your research visible.

Academia is a prestige economy, where individual researchers are often evaluated based on their perceived esteem within their communities. Remaining visible is an essential part of accumulating esteem. An online presence maintained via personal websites, social media accounts (e.g., Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn), researcher identifiers (e.g., ORCID) and academic social networks (e.g., ResearchGate), can be a personal calling card, where you can highlight experience and demonstrate your expertise in certain topics. Being active on important mailing lists and social media is not only a good chance to disseminate your findings to those communities, but also offers you the chance to engage with your community, and potentially spark new ideas and collaborations. Using researcher identifiers like ORCID when disseminating outputs will ensure that those outputs will be unambiguously linked back to the individual researcher (and even automatically updated to their ORCID profile). The OpenUP survey showed that nearly half of the respondents (41%) use academic social networks as a medium to disseminate their research and a quarter of respondents (26%) said that these networks informed their professional work.

For projects, similar principles apply. Create a brand by giving your project a unique name, ideally with some intuitive relation to the issue you are investigating. Create a striking visual identity, with a compelling logo, core colours and project slogan. Create a website which leverages this visual identity, that is as simple and intuitive as possible, both in its layout and in the way content is formulated (limit insider jargon). Make sure to keep old content up to date and to add new content frequently in order to incentivise stakeholders to re-visit. Create associated appropriate social media accounts (e.g., Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, SlideShare, YouTube) and link to this from the project website. Aim for a constant presence with new content to reinforce project messaging. Include links to other project online presences such as social media accounts. Consider including a blog to disseminate core findings or give

important project updates. A periodical newsletter could be released in order to provide project updates and other news, to keep the community informed and activated regarding project issues. Depending on the size of your project and budget, you might want to produce hardcopy material such as leaflets or factsheets, as well as branded giveaways to increase awareness of your project.

5.6 Step 6: Go live

In person dissemination doesn't just have to be at stuffy conferences – hit the road and take part in science festivals, science slams, TEDx talks, science festivals, or roadshows.

With research moving outside the walls of universities, there are several types of places for participatory research. Next to classic scientific conferences, different types of events addressing wider audiences have emerged.

Science slams are short talks where researchers explain a scientific topic to a non-expert audience. Similar to other short talk formats like TED talks, they lend themselves to being spread over YouTube and other video channels. Giulia Enders won the first prize in a science slam that took place on the 5th of March 2012 in Berlin with her fascinating talk about the gut. The YouTube video of her talk received over 1 mil views. After this success she got an offer to write a book about the gut and the digestive system. Her book "Darm mit Charme" was translated, among others, into English, French and Italian. Science Shops for example are small entities which provide independent, participatory research support to civil society. While they are usually linked to universities, hacker and maker spaces tend to be community-run locations, where people with an interest in science, engineering, and art meet and collaborate on projects. Science festivals are community-based showcases of science and technology which take place over large areas for several days or weeks and directly involve STEM researchers and practitioners in public outreach. Less formally, Science Cafés or similar events like Pint of Science are public engagement events in casual settings like pubs and coffeehouses.

Alternatively, for a more personal approach, consider reaching out to key stakeholders who might be affected by your research and requesting a meeting. Such an approach can be especially powerful in getting the message across to decision-makers and thought-leaders, although the resources required to schedule and potentially travel to such meetings means you should target such activities very carefully. And don't forget the value of serendipity - who knows who you'll meet in the course of your everyday meetings and travels. Always be prepared with a 30 second "elevator-pitch" that sums up your project in a confident and concise manner - such encounters may be the gateways to greater engagement.

5.7 Step 7: Think visual

Dissemination of research is still largely ruled by the written or spoken word. However, there are many ways to introduce visual elements which can act as attractive means to help your audiences understand and interpret your research. Disseminate findings through art or multimedia interpretations. Let your artistic side loose or use new visualisation techniques to produce intuitive, attractive data displays.

Most obviously, this could take the form of data visualization. Graphic representation of quantitative information reaches back to "earliest map-making and visual depiction" (Friendly, 2008). As technologies have advanced so have our means of visually representing data. Powerful tools for data visualization now mean that researchers can produce arresting images which add clarity to their research.

Science comics can be used, in the words of McDermott et al. (McDermott et al., 2018), to "communicate difficult ideas efficiently, illuminate obscure concepts, and create a metaphor that can be much more memorable than a straightforward description of the concept itself". McDermott et al. continue that comics can be used to punctuate or introduce papers or presentations, to capture and share the

content of conference talks, and that some journals even have a “cartoon” publication category. They advise that such content has a high chance of being “virally” spread via social media.

As previously discussed, you may also consider creating a video abstract for a paper or project.

Projects have even successfully disseminated scientific findings through art. For example, the Civilians - a New York based investigative theatre company - received a three-year grant to develop *The Great Immensity*⁸, a play addressing the complexity of climate change. *AstroDance*⁹ tells the story of the search for gravitational waves through a combination of dance, multi-media, sound and computer simulations. The annual Dance Your PhD contest, which began in 2007 and is sponsored by Science magazine, even asks scientists to interpret their PhD research as dance.¹⁰

5.8 Step 8: Respect diversity

Research should reach all who might be affected by it. Respect inclusion in scientific dissemination by creating messages which reflect gender, demography and ability diversity.

The discourse on academic diversity has always included discussions on gender, ethnic and cultural backgrounds, or economic diversity. However, diversity, as the representation of different types of people in regard to gender, race, ability or religion, on its own right, is not an adequate concept to talk about the scholarly divergence.

There is no question about the necessity of diversity in this field. Science can be viewed as a competition of ideas and theories, where the most supported theories come on top, and science gets better and best supports social and economic transformations if the pool of ideas is wider to draw from. However, it is not enough to make our platforms and channels of scientific communication diverse, but we have to make a conscious effort to keep the participants included in the long run.

The 2017 Progression Framework benchmarking report of the Scientific Council has made several recommendation how to make progress on diversity and inclusion in science: (1) a strategy and action plan for diversity should developed which requires action from all members included, (2) diversity should be included in a wide range of scientific activities, such as building diversity into prizes, awards or, creating guidance on building diversity and inclusion across a range of demographics groups into communications, and building diversity and inclusion into education and training (Bond and Shapiro, 2017).

To broaden activity beyond gender and age to include other aspects of diversity is not an easy task though. There are several challenges have to be overcome in creating an inclusive environment. In order to advance progress data are needed, beyond gender and age (the primary common demographic information available for scientific evaluation on diversity). Progress in inclusivity should be monitored in a quantitative way for which evidence is required. The communication of success stories might help to boost actions on diversity and inclusion when progress might be slow. Promoting a dialogue and a greater understanding of why diversity and inclusion is beneficial for scientific communication is important.

Key points to consider for more inclusive innovative dissemination activities are: (1) diversity within the team responsible for research and dissemination, (2) representation of diversity within disseminated materials, (3) sensitivity to the diversity of audiences in the use of dissemination tools, plat-

⁸ <http://thegreatimmensity.org/>

⁹ <http://astrodance.rit.edu/>

¹⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dance_Your_PhD

forms, methods and strategies. In regards to the latter, it is especially important to create materials that conform to standards for accessibility to enable people with disabilities can use them.¹¹

5.9 Step 9: Find the right tools

Innovative dissemination practices often require different resources and skills than traditional dissemination methods. As a result of different skills and tools needed, there may be higher costs associated with some aspects of innovative dissemination. You can find tools via the OpenUP Hub: openuphub.eu/disseminate/services

The OpenUP Hub (openuphub.eu) is an open, dynamic and collaborative knowledge environment that systematically captures, organizes and categorizes research outcomes, best practices, tools, and guidelines relevant to review-dissemination-assessment phases of the research lifecycle through the prism of Open Science. OpenUP Hub addresses all key stakeholders engaged in the research lifecycle: researchers, young scholars, educators, publishers, R&I project members, policy makers & funders, IT providers and citizens. It is an integrated solution that supports the community needs by offering the right tools for the relevant stakeholders to open up science. It provides a Toolbox of tailored-made solutions and trainings, an Observatory that senses the community pulse, a Blog and a Q&A forum to promote the two-way communication and a Calendar to share major events of the field. Via the “Disseminate” section of the OpenUP Hub, users can access training materials, guidelines, case-studies, background readings, and a categorised list of innovative dissemination service.

Figure 9. OpenUP Hub catalogue of innovative dissemination services
<https://www.openuphub.eu/disseminate/services>

The Hub lists a catalogue of innovative dissemination services, organised according to the following categories:

- **Visualizing data:** tools to help create innovative visual representations of data
- **Sharing notebooks, protocols and workflows:** ways to share outputs that document and share research processes, including notebooks, protocols & workflows
- **Crowdsourcing & collaboration:** platforms that help researchers and those outside academia to come together to perform research and share ideas
- **Profiles & networking:** platforms to raise academic profile and find collaboration and funding opportunities with new partners

¹¹ <https://www.w3.org/standards/webdesign/accessibility>

- **Organizing events:** tools to help plan, facilitate and publicise academic events
- **Outreach to wider public:** channels to help broadcast your research to audiences beyond academia, including policy makers, young people, industry and broader society
- **Publishing:** platforms, tools and services to help you publish your research
- **Archive and share:** pre-print servers and repositories to help you archive and share your texts, data, software, posters and more

5.10 Step 10: Evaluate, evaluate, evaluate

Assess your dissemination activities. Are they having the right impact? If not, why not? Evaluation of dissemination efforts is an essential part of the process. In order to know what worked and which strategies did not generate the desired outcomes, all the research activities should be assessed. Such evaluation should be measured via the use of quantitative and qualitative indicators (which should be already foreseen in the planning stage of dissemination, see Step 1). Questionnaires, interviews, observations and assessments could also be used to measure the impact. Defining indicators relating to the different project activities should be foreseen at the start of the project and part of the overall dissemination plan. Assessing and identifying the most successful practices, will give you the evidence for the most effective strategies to reach your audience. In addition, the evaluation can help you plan your further budget and minimise the spending and dedicating efforts on ineffective dissemination methods.

Some examples of quantitative indicators:

- Citations of publications;
- Alternative metrics related to websites and social media platforms (updates, visits, interactions, likes and reposts);
- Numbers of events held for specific audiences;
- Numbers of participants those events;
- Production and circulation of printed materials;
- Media coverage (articles in specialised press newsletters, press releases, interviews, etc.);

Some examples of qualitative indicators:

- Visibility in the social media and attractiveness of website;
- Newly established contacts with networks and partners and the outcomes of these contacts;
- Feedback from the target groups;
- Share feedback within your group on what dissemination strategies seemed to be the most effective in conveying your messages and reaching your target audiences.

6. Conclusions

OpenUP Work Package 4 has aimed to investigate innovative ways of disseminating research outputs beyond traditional academic dissemination in different disciplines. Such ways include the dissemination of research results in traditional media (e.g. newspapers, TV), social media (e.g. via blogging), or museums, using text, images, videos, games, comics and other media formats. Such dissemination media and methods can support researchers in creating impact, help spread scientific results to wider audiences (e.g. the industry, policy makers, specialists outside the research community, journalists, the general public), as well as (in disseminating results via interactive Web tools) make transparent how research outputs are used in non-research communities and the general public, which can deliver further impact evidence relevant for researchers, funders and other stakeholders. Work within OpenUP addresses a variety of stakeholders, including researchers, institutions, funders, publishers, and citizens. To analyse the needs and attitudes of these groups, we employed multiple instruments including literature review, an extensive survey of European researchers, case studies of projects employing innovative dissemination methods, interactive workshops, and interviews.

This deliverable report has synthesised work across the OpenUP project to investigate innovative dissemination to provide insights into current practices, classify and assess methods and tools, and provide scenario-based case studies. The identified practices and methods have been validated in cooperation with other work packages to analyse the influence of Open Science practices on the impact and visibility of research outputs. Drawing together the rich results of these various strands of work, we can draw the following conclusions:

Dissemination is increasingly participatory and multi-directional: The OpenUP investigation of innovative dissemination methods revealed a wealth of approaches going beyond traditional academic publishing, and gathered success stories and good practices from all over the world. In particular, the analysis demonstrated the potential of digital technologies for involving audiences beyond the usual dissemination targets to actively involve peers or citizens that would otherwise be out of reach. Dissemination in an open science context is increasingly done at earlier stages of the research lifecycle and is thus becoming an integral part of the whole research workflow. In addition, dissemination becomes more interactive; as a result, it is often difficult to draw the line between the activities of dissemination and participation. This was confirmed by our crowdsourcing of examples of innovative dissemination for the case studies. This activity connected OpenUP to peers in open science and in the research community, and informed them of the project goals and early results.

Innovative dissemination is integral to Open Science: Open Science is rooted in principles of participation and transparency, enabling others to collaborate in, contribute to, scrutinise and re-use research and spread knowledge as widely as possible. As such, innovative dissemination is a core aim of Open Science. However, when it comes to openness, even the most innovative dissemination efforts, such as the Pluto Fly-By may not provide materials that can be used, modified or shared. Hence, researchers need guidance in all aspects of Open Science, including choosing the right license for their materials in order to achieve the highest possible reuse of their materials.

A proliferation of channels: The variety of innovative dissemination methods found in the case studies was further broadened in the survey, where we received more than 100 descriptions of use of innovative dissemination methods and tools. There have never been more avenues for the dissemination of research, and yet researchers remain largely focused on just a few traditional outputs (journal articles, books, conference presentations).

Enthusiasm is not reflected in uptake: While we can observe enthusiastic uptake with specific groups of researchers, the OpenUP survey results also showed that there is a gap in practice when it comes to innovative dissemination. While we can observe enthusiastic uptake with specific groups of researchers, the survey results also showed that there is a gap in practice when it comes to innovative

dissemination. Even though 71% of researchers agreed that it is important to disseminate to non-research audiences, all of the dissemination channels specifically designed for doing so are used only by less than a third of researchers on a regular basis. Communicating to a wider audience seems therefore to be more of a developing norm with enthusiastic early adopters than a widely exercised practice. This is emphasized by the fact that only 12% of respondents reported to having achieved an outstanding result using innovative dissemination channels. In addition, two thirds reported to start with the dissemination only after the conclusion of research. When asked about the reasons for not using innovative dissemination channels, next to organisational reasons (time, money, credit), lack of knowledge of innovative dissemination channels and methods is mentioned by 40% of respondents. This share is even higher for young researchers.

Gender and diversity are vital elements: Success in research and innovation is best served by the efficient contribution of all useful viewpoints. Ensuring that all voices get heard despite ongoing social biases and inequities in distribution of resources requires respecting diversity in science. With respect to gender, for example, we have identified four relevant aspects: (1) the gender distribution within the team responsible for research and dissemination, (2) representation of gender in the disseminated materials, (3) gender sensitivity and inclusiveness of the used dissemination tools, platforms and strategies, and (4) gender aspect related to the target audience.

The importance of systematic experimentation with new methods of innovative dissemination: The technological and social conditions for the dissemination of research are evolving so quickly that it is essential that researchers remain alert to new possibilities and willing to systematically investigate possible issues in implementation – as with, for example, our investigation of needed standards and practices for data publishing.

The need for advice tailored to particular stakeholders: In scoping the needs for disseminating to businesses and the public, it has become clear that a diverse approach for defining and supporting open science dissemination is needed. There is no one size fits all. The division in the two above mentioned target groups has proven not to be necessarily evident or useful for all projects. The division into these two main target groups is rather arbitrary and cannot necessarily be applied to other specific target groups. A more diverse approach to defining and supporting open science dissemination is needed (e.g. including other target groups or addressing trans-disciplinary questions).

The link between alternative metrics and innovative dissemination: Alternative metrics provide efficient feedback on the success or otherwise of many innovative dissemination activities. Interpreting these statistics, however, requires not only familiarity with platforms which deliver such metrics, but also with the ways in which they are calculated and the ways in which they might misrepresent real impact. Hence, better training and awareness of alternative metrics will enhance successful take-up of innovative dissemination.

Uptake can be fostered through training and support activities: Training and awareness activities are vital in alerting researchers and others of the value of innovative dissemination. Funders and research organisations can incorporate such training into other activities. Hence, integrating simple steps into research processes will embed innovative dissemination in scholarly workflows. By presenting ten simple steps to innovative dissemination in the next section, we will attempt to show how small changes in research dissemination can have a large impact.

There is an urgent need to incentivise innovative dissemination: Novel dissemination practices are often not on the agendas of policy makers, national research funders or research institutions. Innovative dissemination activities not reflected in reward schemes which are still heavily skewed towards traditional outputs. In order to make such activities count in research life and hence foster uptake, rewards and incentives should be adjusted.

Innovative dissemination could be enabled by a new class of professionals: Targeted and interactive Open Science Communication should be supported on policy and institutional level to increase active participation by researchers. In this context, additional funding of science communication activities, setting appropriate incentives and providing communication and soft-skills training for researchers are key factors. To fill this gap, we propose to create new science communication roles and positions to be staffed with people both skilled in science communication and with science expert knowledge. It is important to have, next to PR and marketing staff, trained experts with the necessary scientific background and skills, who are also trained in communicating to and interacting with audiences outside the research community by means of Web 2.0 technologies.

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8. Appendix 1: Case studies

8.1 Introduction

OpenUP conducted a range of compact case studies to gain an understanding of the effectiveness, suitability and impact of currently applied approaches. For that, we performed a landscape scan of existing research projects that used innovative dissemination methods and tools. The scan was performed in two steps: an internal collection of leads within the project, and a crowdsourcing phase, where we invited collaborators outside the project to provide additional examples.

In the internal collection, we identified 16 projects and 8 methods & tools. This collection was used as an input for the crowdsourcing phase. We entered the leads into a Google Spreadsheet, modelled after the best practice example of the 101 Innovations in Scholarly Communications project. Then, we opened up the process to the community and collected additional input in a crowd-sourced way. To this end, we disseminated the spreadsheet via mailing lists and the project's Twitter and Facebook accounts asking for further examples. The crowdsourcing phase ran from October 4-23, 2016. During this time, we received 39 further leads (18 projects, 21 platforms/methods).

In total, we collected 34 projects and 29 tools/methods. The project/dissemination type was assigned in a qualitative analysis of the leads. The analysis revealed that citizen science/crowdsourcing was the most popular type with 15 projects. Next are public information/outreach projects (5 leads), projects focussing on education (4), and projects disseminating mostly within academia (4). We also received 2 leads for each of the following types: viral dissemination, EU/international project, and high-profile events. From these leads we selected 10 cases to be representative of a range of practices, disciplines and regions, which we analysed in depth.

8.2 Methodology

The cases were analysed along seven dimensions and 18 specific dimensions (see Table 8). The dimensions were defined based on (1) the literature review, especially the analysis of dissemination frameworks (see section 2.1.1), (2) the focus topics of the project and (3) the requirements of the framework and toolbox.

Table 8. Main dimensions and specific dimensions analysed for the 10 selected case studies

Main dimension	Specific dimension
Why?	Purpose of dissemination
What and How?	Dissemination activities, Dissemination outputs, Tools used, Disseminated materials, Media formats
When?	Start of dissemination, Dissemination phases
Who?	Who initiated the dissemination? Target Audience, Reception and Impact
Effort	Quality of materials, Estimated cost
Openness	Openness of dissemination, Interoperability, Connection to peer review and metrics
Gender	Distribution of gender in project, Representation of gender in materials

The first four main dimensions include the classic “6 Ws”, with the “Where?” implicitly included in the “What and How?”. They cover the input factors of the Communication-Persuasion matrix (source, channel, message, audience, and setting). The effort needed was added as a specific requirement of the toolbox as this is an important dimension for researchers. This fact is also evidenced in the survey results where researchers named time and resources as major barriers to innovative dissemination. Openness and gender were included as cross-cutting focus topics of the project. In terms of openness, we investigated the openness of disseminated materials, their interoperability, and if there was any

the connection to open peer review and metrics. For assessing openness, we used the Open Definition¹²:

“Open means anyone can freely access, use, modify, and share for any purpose (subject, at most, to requirements that preserve provenance and openness).”

To generate the estimates for the cost dimension, we assumed the role of a researcher in Central Europe, who has all the skills of a trained researcher, but does not know about things like graphic design, web design or video production. He or she thus has to purchase external services. Based on this scenario, we made an estimate what the services would cost and put them into three categories:

- 1) Low: < EUR 5,000
- 2) Medium: < EUR 50,000
- 3) High: >= EUR 50,000

Note that we did not include the time that is spent by the researchers themselves in the dissemination activities. This is highly dependent on the skills of the researcher and the extent of the activity.

With regards to gender, we strived to address relevant gender-sensitive implications of the analysed innovative dissemination approaches. To understand the effectiveness, suitability and impact of currently applied dissemination approaches, as well as related risks for both male and female actors it is necessary to take into account how biological, cultural and social features of gender are relevant in this context.

In general, opening scholarly communication and dissemination to private and public stakeholders using innovative communication channels has implications in terms of how scientific content is represented and communicated. In this context, an important aspect is to reflect how sex and gender are represented and perceived in the various media. Important related questions are: What is the gender impact of dissemination material? Is gender and diversity taken into account? Does the dissemination material design take into account gender sensitive and inclusive communication (language, content)? Are there any negative effects for male or female end users of the innovative dissemination materials (e.g. exclusion, prevailing masculinity/femininity norms)?

Next to that, the changing dissemination strategies in research might have different implications for male and female researchers. Important questions in this context are: Are there any negative effects for male or female users of the innovative dissemination channels (e.g. exclusion, prevailing masculinity/femininity norms)? Are the dissemination strategies products of male- or female-oriented processes?

In the following sections, we present the 10 case studies in a compact form along the main dimensions.

¹² <http://opendefinition.org/>

8.3 Pluto Fly-By

Table 9. Factsheet of the Pluto Fly-By case

Factsheet	
Project Lead	NASA
Discipline	Astronomy
Type	High-profile events
Link	https://www.nasa.gov/mission_pages/newhorizons/main/index.html

Why?

NASA's New Horizons probe has visited a place never before visited by a robotic probe from earth: Pluto. In July 2015, the spacecraft completed a nearly-decade-long journey to fly by Pluto, and revealed humanity's first close-up look at the distant dwarf planet (Dwarf planet). The goal of the dissemination was to communicate results of the mission and facts about Pluto to the broader audience.

Who?

NASA as a first party in the project initiated the dissemination. The aim was to target the general public as an audience, by revealing interesting facts about Pluto to the audience and presenting the results in a simplified way.

What & How?

Different dissemination activities were conducted, such as a Twitter campaign¹³, live streams¹⁴, YouTube videos^{15,16} and press, by disseminating text, video, data, software and simulations¹⁷.

Outputs of the dissemination activities were very rich and can be categorized into images, series of videos, live streams, simulation software, blogs, scientific data, reports and scientific articles.

When?

Certain dissemination activities are evident after the second and third research life-cycle phases - Instrument development and Data Collection/Implementation. However, most of the dissemination takes place after having important results, findings, i.e., in the fifth research life-cycle phase - Publication.

Relation to Open Science

The rights of the published scientific results, images and videos are held by NASA. The FreeFlyer simulation software is proprietary commercial software, whereas the NASA's Eyes software is developed by the California Institute of Technology, so they hold the rights. For scientific articles published by Nature or Elsevier the rights are managed by the corresponding publisher.

Scientific data gathered during the mission that are publicly available can be used by researchers for further investigations. Scientific articles underwent a classical peer review process. Available alternative metrics are: the number of newspaper headlines, number of views of YouTube videos, number of tweets or number of downloads of the simulation software.

It can therefore be concluded that NASA followed the paradigm of a rather closed research activity.

Effort

¹³ <https://twitter.com/hashtag/plutoflyby?lang=de>

¹⁴ <https://livestream.com/GriffithObservatoryTV/plutoflyby/videos/93095775>

¹⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Eo3EJYo2dX8>

¹⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=O6BBgLGgB7g&t=12s>

¹⁷ <https://eyes.nasa.gov/eyes-on-pluto.html>

Within the Pluto fly by project, very professional and high quality dissemination materials are produced (i.e., high quality videos, reports or NASA's Eyes simulation software). Based on the methodology for generating the estimates for the cost dimension described in section 8.2, the costs are estimated to be high (\geq EUR 50,000).

Impact

Followed by social media, press, TV, made international headlines; it became the perfect media storm. The Pluto story was on the cover of more than 450 newspapers in multiple languages. The New Horizons team produced new images of Pluto with analysis and informed members of the general public about new discoveries on Pluto.

Gender

The first party of the project is NASA (compared to other projects, in which founders are individuals), thus, it is not so easy to identify the gender dimension in this project. According to some blogs, men (maybe in majority) and women are represented in the team of NASA behind Pluto fly-by. However, due to the scope of the project, the gender sensitive language is not visible in the dissemination materials. For example, the NASA team is mentioned as a team, without distinguishing between male and female.

Highlight

Method: "Pluto in a Minute" videos

NASA broke down interesting facts about Pluto and findings from the mission in one minute long videos. In each video, a NASA scientist talks about a specific topic, e.g. Pluto's moons; the findings are visualized using stills and animations. The "Pluto in a Minute" videos provide interesting bits of information about Pluto in a way that is understandable for an interested audience. A similar format is Minute Physics, which are done in the RSA Animate style.

8.4 Galaxy Zoo

Table 10. Factsheet of the Galaxy Zoo case

Factsheet	
Project Lead	Chris Lintott and Kevin Schawinski
Discipline	Astronomy
Type	Citizen science project
Link	https://www.galaxyzoo.org/

Why?

Galaxy Zoo is a well-known online citizen science project (Sauermaun and Franzoni 2014), where the general public is directly involved in research activities. It is now available on the platform Zooniverse.org that is currently the largest aggregator of crowd science projects in various disciplines. Galaxy Zoo is a project which invites people to assist in the morphological classification of large numbers of galaxies through a website. Citizens classifying galaxies help scientists to understand how galaxies evolved over time and test theories about the nature of the Universe.

The purpose of dissemination is twofold: sharing research data in the format of galaxy images and involving citizens in the analysis of these scientific data.

Who?

Chris Lintott and Kevin Schawinski are the founders of the project; they initiated the dissemination actions that addressed the general public, as a target audience.

What & How?

The Galaxy Zoo website is the primary source of dissemination of the project activities. It includes a blog¹⁸ and a forum¹⁹ that support the volunteers in the discussion, analysis and classification of galaxies. Other dissemination activities are videos available on YouTube, releases and news articles in important journals and TV (Times Online, USA today, Spiegel online, BBC news, etc.). The main dissemination contents are images, video, text and data.

The dissemination project outputs are both galaxy images associated with the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS)²⁰, available on the *ad hoc* developed Galaxy Zoo website, and the results presented in scientific articles and open-source sets of the analysed data.

When?

Dissemination activities started in an early stage of the project with the aim to share the project objectives and involve of a large number of volunteers in the analysis of images. During the data collection and analysis process, SDSS images were available on the website along with their classification provided by citizen scientists supported also through Galaxy Zoo Blog and Talk. Also teaching materials were shared to support teachers and educators. In the last phase, the results of analysis are presented in scientific articles and gathered in open access datasets.

Relation to Open Science

Galaxy Zoo is released under a Creative Commons license, but the design and graphical elements of the site, including the logo, are separately copyrighted. Also galaxy images are governed by the SDSS copyright policy. Project results are open to a large number of potential contributors. Raw data can be used for novel knowledge production. All data related to the project and scientific publications are available in specific sections on the project website. Data are also retrievable through links in the published papers.

¹⁸ <https://blog.galaxyzoo.org/>

¹⁹ <https://talk.galaxyzoo.org/>

²⁰ <http://www.sdss.org/>

The majority of scientific articles are submitted to arXiv, one of the best-known preprint open archive that is based on a moderator system in charge of reclassification and/or removals of the submitted article. arXiv has download metrics on the entire archive.

Effort

Galaxy Zoo involves a lot of professionals and uses high quality tools. The website was created by a web design company. The Galaxy Zoo Blog and Talk are moderated by specialists. The galaxy images come from the Sloan Digital Sky Survey and are high quality.

The website was developed by an external service; costs can be estimated as low-medium, ranging from EUR 5,000 to EUR 50,000.

Impact

Followed by news and social media as well as research institutions, Galaxy Zoo has had a great success and has reached a large audience. Concerning scientific impact, the project played an important role in new knowledge and scientific advancement. The experiment was successful so that the original Galaxy Zoo project²¹, which ran from July 2007 until February 2009, was replaced by Galaxy Zoo 2, Galaxy Zoo: Hubble, and Galaxy Zoo: CANDELS.

Gender

There are no specific initiatives targeted to women. The project is developed by two men who are engaged in every phase of project dissemination. The working team is composed of more men than women. According to an online survey (Raddick et al. 2010) on volunteers' motivations for participating to Galaxy Zoo, male volunteers (80%) are more represented than female volunteers.

Highlight

Educational tool: ZooTeach

ZooTeach is a website where teachers and educators can share high quality lesson plans and resources that complement all Zooniverse citizen science projects. Lessons can be retrieved by age groups and subject areas that also comprise the topics related to Galaxy Zoo.

²¹ <http://zoo1.galaxyzoo.org/>

8.5 Polymath Project

Table 11. Factsheet of the Polymath Project case

Factsheet	
Project Lead	Timothy Gowers and Michael Nielsen
Discipline	Mathematics
Type	Within academia/research community
Link	https://polymathprojects.org

Why?

Polymath projects, also known as massively collaborative online mathematics, represents a form of open Internet collaboration aimed towards a major mathematical goal, usually to solve yet unsolved mathematical problems.

Who?

The dissemination of the project was initiated by the founders of the project: Timothy Gowers and Michael Nielsen through Gowers's blog entitled "Is massively collaborative mathematics possible?"²² released in January 2009. Additionally, Terence Tao started to work very actively in the dissemination, shortly after Gowers's blog was released. Their aim was to target mathematicians that are motivated to bring new ideas and exchange them with others in order to solve difficult math problems, but also academics, teachers, students and other individuals interested in maths.

What & How?

Dissemination is conducted in terms of text and video through public information blogs (Gowers 2009 & Terence Tao's Blog), the home page, wiki pages (Polymath Wiki page)²³, the Q&A site MathOverflow (MathOverflow)²⁴ and YouTube videos (Terence Tao's videos)^{25,26}. There are papers available that describe the outcomes of the Polymath projects, which are uploaded to arXiv and are also submitted to the Journal of Mathematics of Computation or Nature (DHJ Polymath 2014, Tao et. al. 2012, and Gowers and Nielsen 2009).

When?

The focus of the PolyMath project was to start with the dissemination in the very early stages of the project. So, the most important dissemination activities took place after the first research life-cycle phase - Design. From the first dissemination activities, new opportunities and projects were created. In general, dissemination is noticeable after each research life-cycle phase.

Relation to Open Science

Based on the policy of the Polymath project, all collaboration records, outcomes and results are generally accessible to the public audience, so that they can be reused by mathematicians. The results of a Polymath project, for example, helped to solve problems defined in another Polymath project.

Nevertheless, the outcomes are not explicitly put under a permissive license. For articles published in arXiv, for example, rights are only granted to arXiv.org (i.e., a perpetual, non-exclusive license to distribute the articles), and for Nature journal articles, rights are managed by the Nature Publishing Group.

²² <https://gowers.wordpress.com/2009/01/27/is-massively-collaborative-mathematics-possible/>

²³ http://michaelnielsen.org/polymath1/index.php?title=Main_Page

²⁴ <http://mathoverflow.net/questions/219638/proposals-for-polymath-projects>

²⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jCUcdsXbqYc>

²⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=elWIDVI6b18>

Particular problems and proposed solutions are reviewed and discussed by the members of each Polymath project in corresponding pages and blogs. There is, however, no evidence that the number of upvotes of the proposed math problems in MathOverflow is one of the criteria that proposals turn to Polymath projects - at least this is not explicitly stated. When defining the criteria, the Polymath community has rather been focusing on projects in the fields of algebraic geometry, algebraic topology, group theory, logic, and set theory.

Effort

YouTube videos of Terence Tao can be characterized as high quality videos. Public blogs are managed and moderated by individuals. Similarly, wiki and Q&A sites are managed by members of individual projects. Hence, dissemination costs can be estimated as medium (< EUR 50,000).

Impact

The project has been very well received by the target audience; the first problem introduced in the first Polymath project has been solved within one and a half months. Since then, the Polymath project solved very difficult mathematical problems or made progress in solving them.

Polymath papers are usually signed with a group pseudonym that consists of the initials of Polymath project title. A link to the full working record is also provided. So, for authors it is a bit difficult to list such publications in their CVs, for example, or increase their visibility. Authors/participants got more informal recognitions, because people were following their work, their blogs, but there is a lack of a formal recognition (Terence Tao's videos). However, there are peer reviewed papers that investigate in detail the concept, scope and impact of Polymath projects.

Gender

Co-founders of the project (Timothy Gowers and Michael Nielsen) and persons playing a major role in the dissemination (i.e., Terence Tao) are men. As a characteristic for the discipline of the project (mathematics), most of the collaborators in the Polymath projects are men. The proposed math problems that became Polymath projects were also contributed by men. There is no evidence of any dissemination activity targeted at women. The language used in the dissemination materials and communication channels seems not to be gender sensitive.

Highlight

Method: Blog post

With his blog "Is massively collaborative mathematics possible?" (released January 2009), Timothy Gowers managed to gain the attention of many mathematicians that started to discuss very difficult problems in mathematics by commenting on his blog. Collaboration continued by defining unsolved problems and solving them, or making progress on solving them. As a very important fact, results of a particular Polymath project were used as inputs that helped to solve problems in other Polymath projects.

8.6 Brain Projects Think Big

Table 12. Factsheet of the Brain Projects Think Big case

Factsheet	
Project Lead	Idan Segev and Felix Schürmann on Frontiers for Young Minds
Discipline	Neuroscience
Type	Focus on teaching
Link	https://kids.frontiersin.org/article/10.3389/frym.2013.00008

Why?

The article “Brain Projects Think Big”²⁷ was published October 13, 2013, the early stages of the Human Brain Project²⁸. The goal was to provide a younger audience with an understanding of the Human Brain Project. The project is primarily a systematic cataloguing of everything that is known about the brain, as well as, the development of ingenious experimental and theoretical methods to probe the brain, and put together all learnings into a computer model of the brain.

Who?

Neuroscientists Idan Segev and computer scientist Felix Schürmann shared information about the brain to a younger audience ages 8-15 on the Frontiers for Young Minds²⁹ – Understanding Neuroscience journal.

Frontiers for Young Minds was launched in 2013 as a non-profit scientific journal written by scientists and reviewed by a board of young students. Today, it has five sections: (1) Understanding Neuroscience, (2) Understanding Astronomy and Space Science, (3) Understanding Biodiversity, (4) Understanding Health, and (5) Understanding the Earth and its Resources.

As a journal, Frontiers for Young Minds provides a platform for young people to work with scientists, ask informed, critical questions and give feedback. By working directly with scientists, Frontiers for Young Minds ensures that the published article is relevant scientific research. By working directly with young students, Frontiers for Young Minds helps foster curiosity in and out of the classroom and engage the next generation of citizens and scientists.

What & How?

The Human Brain Project used traditional dissemination (Markram 2006, Druckmann et al. 2012). Publishing a child friendly version of the Human Brain Project on the Frontiers for Young Minds platform was an innovative approach to reach a different audience.

When?

Dissemination started at the same time as the launch of the Human Brain Project. As a next phase, the project plans to open a “brain corner” in many science museums worldwide to share updates and important results.

Relation to Open Science

Brain Project Thinks Big was reviewed by a young student, mentored by a scientist with experience in peer review to guide the peer review process. It is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY). PDF download is available. The count of abstract views, full text views and PDF download is available online.

Effort

²⁷ <https://kids.frontiersin.org/article/10.3389/frym.2013.00008>

²⁸ <https://www.humanbrainproject.eu>

²⁹ <https://kids.frontiersin.org/>

Frontiers for Young Minds produced the videos, and media materials at a low cost (<5,000 EUR). For the same effort, external graphics design, web design and video production, a researcher will spend the same (< 5,000 EUR).

Impact

As of this writing, the count of abstract views: 20, full text views: 117, PDF downloads, 222. The article has been accessed primarily in the United States and China.

Figure 10. Distribution of readers of the article “Brain Projects Think Big”. Source: Frontiers usage data

Gender

From a gender demographic, two male scientists wrote the article - Idan Segev, and Felix Schürmann. It was reviewed by an 11-year old female student, named Abby.

The Frontiers for Young Minds Editorial Board has a 73% to 27% female to male ratio. The Chief Editor is male. Two out of six Specialty Chief Editors are female, and seventeen out of nineteen Associate Chief Editors are women.

Highlight
Method: Focus on teaching

Brain Project Thinks Big was the inaugural issue of the Frontiers for Young Minds in Neuroscience. Seventy other articles in Neuroscience are now available on the platform for younger audience to read and enjoy. The section of Frontiers for Young Minds - Understanding Neuroscience includes articles about the brain, how the brain changes over time, techniques used to study the brain, aspects of the brain that relate to behaviour and performance, and why the brain developed in the ways that it did. Understanding Neuroscience wants to provide a chance for the next generation to think critically about the organ that makes it possible for them to think in the first place.

8.7 Gut (Giulia Enders)

Table 13. Factsheet of the Gut case

Factsheet	
Project Lead	Giulia Enders
Discipline	Medicine
Type	Viral dissemination
Link	http://www.darm-mit-charme.de/

Why?

The Gut project is a one-person project founded by Giulia Enders³⁰, with the aim to explain the functionality of a very complex organ, the gut, in a basic language that is understandable for the general audience. The project also wants to initiate discussions around this topic, which are usually avoided by people.

As a PhD student in Medicine, Enders was fascinated with the functioning of the gut. So she decided to investigate and study this complex organ, the importance of which is usually underestimated. After her success in several science slams in 2012^{31,32} she got an offer to write a book about the gut. Her book (published in March 2014) was a huge success³³, because of the way she explains the complex process of digestion. She presents facts in a simple way, understandable for the broader audience, and she uses a lot of humour at the same time.

Who?

Giuliana Enders, the founder of the project, initiated the dissemination. Her goal was to inform the society as a whole about the importance of a complex organ, the gut, and the process of digestion.

What & How?

One of the first dissemination activities were a number of science slams, in which Giulia Enders gave a talk about the gut. After the science slams and especially after publishing her book “Darm mit Charme” (translated into English, French and Italian) she gained a lot of popularity. She was invited to different TV shows and her story was covered by well-known newspapers. Her book readings were also very well visited.

When?

Dissemination started with the first science slam that took place on 23 January 2012 in Freiburg. Giulia Enders gave a talk about the gut that was very well received from the audience and she won the first prize. The most interesting part of her talk was the way she explained the digestion. She was able to explain a very complex process in a very simple and understandable way and with lots of humour in the same time. Two other science slams, where Giulia Enders also placed first should follow.

So, the first dissemination activity happened (not planned as such) after the Design research life-cycle phase, in terms of the science slam. All other dissemination activities took place after the fifth phase - Publication.

Relation to Open Science

The rights to the book “Darm mit Charme” are held by Ullstein Buchverlage GmbH, Berlin. The YouTube videos are published under the Standard YouTube License. Therefore, none of the materials are open as defined by the Open Definition.

³⁰ <http://www.darm-mit-charme.de/autorin.html>

³¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MFsTSS7aZ5o>

³² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=V1lbAdGnXS8>

³³ <https://www.theguardian.com/books/2014/may/07/gut-reaction-book-digestive-tract-german-bestseller>

Effort

Giulia Enders interviews and her audio book are conducted from professionals and are of a high quality. Dissemination costs are estimated as medium (< EUR 50,000).

Impact

The Gut project was very well received by the target audience. It is Giulia Enders' special way of explaining the gut organ and the complex process of digestion that made this project a huge success. Individuals loved her sense of humour while explaining medicine in such simplified way. From the comments of YouTube videos it is obvious that the Gut project had a huge impact: more than 1 mil copies of the German version of the book have been sold; the science slam videos on YouTube received between 600,000 and 1 mil views.

Gender

The project was founded by women, Giulia Enders, who also wrote the accompanying. No evidence is found about the gender of the readers of her book. From the talks of Giulia Enders and the German version of her book, one can realize that she does not explicitly use gender-sensitive language. To illustrate the point, in German one could distinguish between a male and female scientist - Wissenschaftler/Wissenschaftlerin. In the book illustrations, male and female individuals are equally represented.

Highlight

Method: Science Slam

Science slams are short talks where researchers explain a scientific topic to a non-expert audience. Giulia Enders won the first prize in a science slam that took place on the 5th of March 2012 in Berlin with her fascinating talk about the gut. The YouTube video of her talk received over 1 mil views. After this success she got an offer to write a book about the gut and the digestive system. Her book "Darm mit Charme" was translated, among others, into English, French and Italian.

8.8 Projet SOHA

Table 14. Fact sheet of the Projet SOHA case

Factsheet	
Project Lead	Diéyi Diouf (Senegal) and Florence Piron (Canada)
Discipline	Information science applied to different discipline
Type	Focus on teaching
Link	http://www.projetsoha.org/

Why?

The project "Open Science in Haiti and Francophone Africa (SOHA)³⁴" is part of the OCSD Network³⁵ funded by the International Development Research Centre (IDRC). The project consists of action research, entitled "Open science as a collective tool for development of the power to act and of cognitive justice in Haiti and Francophone Africa: towards a roadmap". The objective is twofold: to understand the obstacles to the emergence of an open science culture in Francophone Africa and Haiti while creating a favourable environment to achieve the goal of an open science culture.

Who?

The researchers Diéyi Diouf and Florence Piron initiated the SOHA project that was launched for a two-year period, from January 2015 to December 2016. It promotes open science as an essential tool for increasing the visibility of scientific work of Francophone Africa and Haiti researchers; therefore its target audience is the academic community.

What & How?

Dissemination consists of several different activities ranging from YouTube videos, newsletters, and scientific events to online training courses, interviews and surveys. The dissemination objects are texts, data and video. The outputs are a network of emerging science shops, a dedicated blog, scientific publications and datasets. However the most important achievement is the consolidation of an international academic community, students, male and female researchers around the concept of cognitive justice.

When?

Dissemination activities started in the early stage of the project with two online surveys and interviews to people involved in the project. During the analysis phase results of questionnaires were available on the website and blog. Researchers were invited to publish their scientific works in open access, with the support of a publishing house: Éditions science et bien commun.

Relation to Open Science

The SOHA project is released under a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license. All outcomes of the project can be freely used by academics, students and researchers generating new knowledge and turning them into new products. It is difficult to define a link between project publications and peer review. Concerning metrics, impact indicators are: number of views for videos, number of downloads for publications in Zenodo as well as project mentions by blogs, tweets, and Facebook pages.

Effort

The project is created and managed by an academic team and all dissemination materials are produced by academics and university students. The project is funded by the International Development Research Centre (IDRC) and the total budget amounts to 80,176.00 CAD\$, i.e. about 50.000 Euro

Impact

³⁴ <http://www.projetsoha.org/>

³⁵ <http://ocsdnet.org/projects/universite-laval/>

The SOHA project is an action project and according to this vocation, it develops a set of actions. These actions include a first survey that received 878 responses in 18 countries, a second one launched in May 2016, four international symposia on open science and cognitive justice, creative journals in Burundi and Niger, a platform for African open access scientific journals, an open book publishing house, etc.

Summing up, the project completely achieved its two aims: a better understanding of the context and importance of open science and an enhancement of the visibility of Francophone Africa and Haiti scientific community. At the moment the project is concluded, but to promote further tangible activities, several members of SOHA created an association called APSOHA that will take over the SOHA project.

Gender

The project was directed by two women. In general, the SOHA project paid special attention to emphasizing the contribution of women in research activities and in the development of open access in the project dissemination material. This is evident in the use of language and images. Concerning language use, masculine and feminine grammatical genders are used (e.g. chercheurs et chercheuses, conseillers et conseillères). In the images male and female are equally represented and they are portrayed also in the same position and situation. These two elements are very important in gender sensitive communication.

Highlight

Science Shops

Science Shops are not "shops" in the traditional sense of the word. They are small entities which provide independent, participatory research support to civil society. Science Shops are often linked to universities where students, under the supervision of a professor, perform the research. Students usually get credit points, counting towards their degrees, for their research. The criteria that most science shops apply are that clients must have no commercial aim with the research, and the research results must become public.

8.9 Science at Home

Table 35. Fact sheet of the Science at Home case

Factsheet	
Project Lead	Jacob Sherson
Discipline	Natural Science
Type	Physics, Cognitive science
Link	https://www.scienceathome.org

Why?

ScienceAtHome is an online platform for collaborative volunteer research, where people are invited to play scientific games, have fun and contribute to real discoveries on quantum physics, and human thinking. The team behind the project consists of scientists, game developers, designers and visual artists based at Aarhus University of Denmark and creates scientific games, with the aim to revolutionise scientific research and teaching by game-play.

The goal of the dissemination is to engage citizens to the project objectives, hence to create a community around the games developed, to maximise the input of results gathered from users' gameplay.

Who?

Dissemination activities have been initiated by Dr. Jacob Sherson, the project leader of ScienceAtHome. Target audiences are researchers, teachers and citizens in general.

What & How?

ScienceAtHome project uses various methods to communicate its objectives to wider audiences and to engage citizens. Its main focal point is set on the use of social media. It has a very active presence on Twitter, Facebook, YouTube and LinkedIn, where it disseminates project updates and news from the science community. Especially the YouTube channel is used to upload videos series about citizen science, quantum physics and game demos and animated videos explaining the concept^{36,37}.

In addition, an important aspect of the ScienceAtHome dissemination activities is the use of gaming elements which lead to the users' engagement (e.g. leaderboard, scoreboard). Another useful tool that the project uses is the Blog. Weekly posts are written by a team of people that is specialised in online community engagement or the official account of ScienceAtHome. Moreover, the project has two Wikipedia references, which also increases its visibility to the general public. The first reference is under the topic of citizen science and the second one under the entry "Quantum Move", an online citizen science simulation video game, which is part of the ScienceAtHome project³⁸. Additionally, physical project presentations like the TED talk at the TEDxAarhus 2016 and the presentation at the NIWeek 2016³⁹ contribute successfully to the outreach of ScienceAtHome to wider audiences.

The project has produced a plethora of dissemination outputs such as images, video series, audio material, software (simulation games), blogs, press references, scientific data and articles.

When?

The year of 2012 was a benchmark for the initiation of dissemination activities of the project. ScienceAtHome took a turn with the first game, Quantum Moves and the team published six (6) scientific papers and started the social media presence (Facebook). Hence, it is observed that the first phase of

³⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC4uHp2YSTDyW9Kcb0TvyR5w>

³⁷ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=X24ombN09_k

³⁸ <https://www.scienceathome.org/games/quantum-moves/>

³⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tQpSOZvrBAC>

dissemination, as well as the ones that followed, can be defined in parallel to important milestones of the project life-cycle phases:

1st phase (Feb 2012): the team started running the first tests of the game in an educational context, in several Danish high schools. The interface was very basic, but there was a very positive initial response.

2nd phase (June 2012): radio appearances and advertisement in aim to recruit volunteers and run a large beta test. 100 volunteers were recruited. The testing results indicated that only a few volunteers succeed in installing the program, and they actually later dropped out because of the complicated interface and the lack of tutorials and informational material.

3rd phase: An effort in systematically testing design hypotheses and assumptions to improve the game experience. The results were made publicly available, in aim to engage more citizens.

4th phase: community management & establishing an online presence. With these activities the team managed to attract 2,000 players to the games. They played the Quantum Moves games roughly 300,000 times⁴⁰.

5th phase: After the first success, the team is ready to tackle the challenge of new scientific problems such understanding general human problem solving (HPS) in order to develop novel artificial intelligence algorithms departing from the Big Data paradigm. So far, cognitive scientists, psychologists and even linguists have joined the ScienceAtHome family.

Relation to Open Science

Research outputs and publications are openly shared via the project website followed by a link to the scientific journal that published the article and a link to arXiv.org where a pdf format of the research article can be found⁴¹. Interestingly, dissemination material and outputs (scientific posters, photographs from events, game images etc.) are available to the general public via a public shared google drive folder (named ScienceAtHome Press Kit) and can be accessed through the project's website.

Effort

The ScienceAtHome project has followed different dissemination approaches aiming to enrol engageable players. Initially, the team has released a respectable number of YouTube videos, using a diverse quality of resources; for instance, the project has produced two high quality videos presenting the aim of the project, a number of animated videos illustrating the games and some non-professional explanatory videos giving insights into the subject of Citizen Science. Additionally, young team members enrich the website content with interesting blog posts. The costs of these dissemination activities can be estimated as medium (< EUR 50,000). Besides these activities, the games produced can be also considered to be taking part in the dissemination efforts of the project; the careful design and interface of the games plays a significant role in the scientific outreach and public engagement. The development cost are estimated to be high (EUR >=50,000).

Impact

Followed by press, radio broadcasts and social media, ScienceAtHome made national and international headlines. Specially, the game Quantum Moves has been played over 8 million times by around 150,000 players around the world with impressive results⁴². After the first success, the scope of project has expanded to additional scientific disciplines and cognitive scientists, psychologists and even linguists have joined the team.

⁴⁰ <https://blog.scienceathome.org/scienceathome-rewinds-part-2/>

⁴¹ <https://www.scienceathome.org/quantum-research/publications>

⁴² <https://www.scienceathome.org/games/quantum-moves/results>

Gender

The project team is divided in 5 groups based on the scope of each team (outreach, didactics, development, design and technical development). Despite the fact that ScienceAtHome is a project with very strong presence of male scientists and faculty (only 25% of team members are female) the Head of outreach is a female scientist. In addition, two female members are responsible for the community management and creating content for online channels. Communicating scientific results and activities to the public is also initiated by other project members as well, creating multiplier effects of the dissemination activities.

Highlight

Method: Game elements

Initiating crowdsourcing can be difficult. ScienceAtHome cleverly used games to overcome this obstacle. People like to participate in a science project but above all, they like games. Using a gaming environment and gaming elements helped ScienceAtHome to gain people's attention and engage with them. A measurable result is that the Quantum Moves games were played 300,000 times (appr.) during their first steps and reached 150k players worldwide.

8.10 Transcribe Bentham

Table 16. Fact sheet of the Transcribe Bentham case

Factsheet	
Project Lead	Melissa Terras – University College London (UCL)
Discipline	Philology
Type	Citizen science project
Link	http://blogs.ucl.ac.uk/transcribe-bentham

Why?

Transcribe Bentham is an online collaborative initiative to transcribe the manuscripts of Jeremy Bentham from the archives of University College London. Jeremy Bentham (1748 – 1832) was an English philosopher, jurist, and social reformer. He is regarded as the founder of modern utilitarianism. The goal of the project is to collaboratively, with the help of many volunteers, digitise valuable handwritten, yet unpublished, work of Jeremy Bentham. By reading and encoding yet unread Bentham's work, new facts can be discovered about his thoughts. In this way, UCL was able to publish new editions of Bentham's work and make them publicly available through the UCL's digital library. Since 2014 Transcribe Bentham is part of the EU-funded Recognition and Enrichment of Archival Documents (READ) project.

Who?

The dissemination was initiated by the founder of the project Melissa Terras, University College London (UCL). With her blog announcement on February 8th 2010 she informed the general public about the launching of the Bentham Papers Transcription Initiative and the secured funds. Work on the project started on March 1st 2010 and the online tool - Transcription Desk is available for contribution since September 7th 2010. The aim was to target the society as a whole, in particular individuals (altruists) interested in Bentham's life and thoughts, history and philosophy, crowdsourcing methodologies and the technology behind the project.

What & How?

Dissemination activities conducted within the project are numerous and vary from public information blogs⁴³, announcements and articles in the press, invited talks, journal articles to Twitter, Facebook posts, Wikipedia article and YouTube videos⁴⁴. One of most important outputs of the project are the digitised/transcribed Bentham manuscripts that are made publicly available. Furthermore, the transcription tool^{45,46} and the software behind it plays a special role in the digitisation process.

When?

The goal of the Transcribe Bentham project was to start with the dissemination in very early stages of the project, right after the first research life-cycle phase - Design, because the transcription through crowdsourcing was identified as very crucial for the success of the project. With the adequate dissemination the founders of the project achieved to attract many volunteers to contribute by transcribing handwritten and unpublished work of Bentham.

Progress update is provided in regular basis in the project homepage/blog informing the general public about the volunteer participation and percentage of the transcribed papers. This indicates that, even though most of dissemination activities took place after the first phase, the dissemination is evident in each of the research life-cycle phases.

⁴³ <http://blogs.ucl.ac.uk/transcribe-bentham/>

⁴⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC2ZXdxpsJwqDKyPUHIfCQ>

⁴⁵ <http://transcriptorium.eu/htr-crowdsourcing-platform-launched/>

⁴⁶ <http://www.transcribe-bentham.da.ulcc.ac.uk/TSX/>

Relation to Open Science

Digitised Bentham's manuscripts are made publicly available through the UCL's digital library under a Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike license (CC BY-NC-SA). This license is not compatible with the Open Definition due to the non-commercial clause. This clause restricts reuse; manuscripts can for example not be reused in Wikipedia due to this clause.

The code for Transcribe Bentham's MediaWiki-based transcription interface is available for reuse and customisation, on an open source basis (GNU General Public License) and can be extended by everyone.

Articles in the International Journal of Humanities and Arts Computing (IJHAC) are not available as open access, whereas some of the book chapters and articles of Melissa Terras are available for download in ResearchGate.

UCL performs surveys to get feedback from volunteers on the transcription tool in order to enhance its functionality and to increase the motivation of volunteers. Volunteers are fully credited in the volumes to which they contribute.

Effort

The disseminated materials such as blogs, videos, software and tutorials are of a high quality and very professional. Thus, dissemination costs are estimated as medium (< EUR 50,000).

Impact

The project is very well received from the general audience and achieves a high number of volunteers. The latest figures (March 2017) manifest this:

"17,842 manuscript pages have now been transcribed or partially-transcribed, which is an increase of 28 on last week's total. Of these transcripts, 16,841 (94%) have been checked and approved by TB (Transcribe Bentham) staff."

The project has received several awards and prizes:

- 2010 Digital Equipment and Database Enhancement for Impact (DEDEFI) Award from the AHRC
- Award of Distinction in the Digital Communities category of the 2011 PrixArs Electronica
- 2012 Platforms for Networked Innovation competition, KNetworks Award

Gender

The founder of the project is a woman, Melissa Terras, who has a major role on the project. The dissemination started with her blog where she asked the general public to contribute in the digitalisation of Bentham's work. Her chapters, books and articles are peer-reviewed and some of them are published in ResearchGate.

Who are the volunteers? According to the volunteer statistics presented in Transcribe Bentham volunteers, two-third of the volunteers that took part in a survey were female. In general, in the dissemination materials and communication there is no evidence of the gender sensitive language.

Highlight

Method: Crowdsourcing

"Many hands make light work. Many hands together make merry work" (Transcribe Bentham blog) - is one of the Bentham's quotes that describes in the best way ever the success of the Transcribe Bentham project. With the

contribution of many volunteers, it was possible to digitise very valuable handwritten yet unpublished work of Jeremy Bentham. As of March 2017, 17,842 manuscript pages have been transcribed or partially-transcribed.

8.11 Homer Multitext Project

Table 47. Factsheet of the Homer Multitext Project case

Factsheet	
Project Lead	Casey Dué and Mary Ebbott, Center for Hellenic Studies, Harvard University
Discipline	Humanities, Classical Philology
Type	Within academia/research community
Link	http://www.homermultitext.org/index.html

Why?

The Homer Multitext (HMT) is a long-term project seeking to present the Homeric Iliad and Odyssey in a critical framework. The project emphasizes collaborative research, openly licensed data, and innovative uses of technology. All material is openly licensed.

HMT invites fellow researchers from all over the world to collaborate in the form of diplomatic editions, images of historical documents, and translations. In this context, the main purpose of dissemination is to reach out to other academic/research communities in the fields (homeric research, digital humanities). The purpose is not only to disseminate the results, but also to stimulate new cooperations, contributions, and ultimately also to share resources among the peers (incl. data, software).

Who?

Dissemination was started by project leaders Casey Dué and Mary Ebbott from the Center for Hellenic Studies, Harvard University. Target audiences are academics and fellow researchers who are interested in building on top of or reusing the Homer Multitext output for their own research work, or in contributing to the Homer Multitext project themselves.

What & How?

In terms of dissemination activities that go beyond traditional academic publishing and attending conferences, the project mainly used the website, a blog⁴⁷, and GitHub⁴⁸ for disseminating their research online. Next to that the project organised summer seminars⁴⁹ as well. The HMT community is also very active on Twitter⁵⁰.

The project had various dissemination outputs. Next to the blog the project published a number of scientific publications, images of scanned manuscripts and transcripts, and a complete edition of the Venetus A manuscript, which is openly available as PDF⁵¹. The disseminated materials include text, photos, a book (the aforementioned PDF), and the HMT software. Media formats include documentation, blog posts, data/transcripts and textual variances, as well as images/scans of manuscripts and source code. The source code and resources on GitHub are being regularly updated.

When?

The first blog post was published in January 2010. Presumably, the website went online during the same year (no information about that is available in the online resources). Beyond the blog and the regular updates on the project website (last March 6, 2016) and GitHub (last March 23, 2017) the HMT community has been very active on Twitter since 2009. A number of conference presentations and scientific publications are presented. Beginning in 2014, citable publications of the HMT project data archive are being released approximately three times per year.

⁴⁷ <http://homermultitext.blogspot.com/>

⁴⁸ <https://github.com/homermultitext>

⁴⁹ <http://www.homermultitext.org/chsseminars.html>

⁵⁰ <https://twitter.com/search?q=homer%20multitext&src=typd>

⁵¹ http://www.homermultitext.org/Pubs/Due_Recapturing_a_Homeric_Legacy.pdf

Relation to Open Science

Homer Multitext has a clear focus on Open Science methods. Not only are all contents of the website licensed openly (CC BY 4.0 license), but also all HMT code is provided open source on GitHub. Documentation (e.g. prerequisite technologies) and guidelines (HMT virtual machine for editors), and further links and tips are provided as well.

Also, data is provided for download and re-use. ZIP files can be manually downloaded from the repository⁵² or retrieved using maven coordinates. All editorial work is kept in simple text files (TEI-conformant XML for HMT texts, and delimited text files, i.e. “.csv” and “.tsv” files, for other structured data).

The current archive of material provisionally accepted for publication is freely available on GitHub. When draft material passes a suite of automated tests, it is accepted in the project central repository.

The HMT project hosts an archive of downloadable images. All images are licensed under terms of various CC licenses. Some copyright holders restrict commercial use.

Effort

HMT produced high-quality multi-text editions of Homer works. The project made high-quality scans of the original manuscripts, related publications and data, software, as well as a book freely and openly accessible.

We estimate the costs for dissemination to be rather low (<5,000 Euros). The dissemination channels and the blog have been curated autonomously at regular intervals by the project members during the course of the project. Although this is not explicitly mentioned in the HMT documentation, we assume that the project did not purchase external services for the production of dissemination material. Rather the project made text and image material resulting from the research and digitisation processes publicly available. Quality of dissemination material can be classified as convenient. Quality of the content seemed to be of higher priority than the form/appearance of the disseminated material. The website design is simple and functional, and so are the data access interfaces. HMT dissemination material was clearly designed to be used by fellow researchers rather than to be made appealing and reusable by other stakeholders (e.g. the general public).

Impact

The project achieved a lot of impact in the research community, especially on Twitter. The project has been mentioned numerous times on Twitter⁵³, and a few times on Facebook⁵⁴. Currently, no forks of the project exist on GitHub.

HMT has 154 undergraduate editors from the US (College of the Holy Cross, University of Houston, University of Washington, Gustavus Adolphus College, Furman, Trinity University, Brandeis University) and the Netherlands (Leiden University), who are contributing on a voluntary basis to the project. 5 of them received Fulbright Fellowships as a direct result of their work⁵⁵.

Gender

The two project leaders, who started the dissemination, are women. For the past five years the project manager was a woman (Stephanie Lindenberg). Neel Smith and Christopher Blackwell are technical

⁵² <http://beta.hpcc.uh.edu/hmt/archival-publications/>

⁵³ <https://twitter.com/search?q=homer%20multitext&src=typd>

⁵⁴ 2013-10-09 by www.facebook.com/haemus.org.mk

2013-05-10 by www.facebook.com/YaleClassicsLibrary

2017-01-05 by www.facebook.com/SocietyforClassicalStudies

2016-02-01 by www.facebook.com/KlassiekeTalenLeiden

⁵⁵ Ch. Blackwell, Philology, Technology, Collaboration. 16 Years of the Homer Multitext. SCA Annual Meeting 2017, Toronto. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XtlzlpkQz68&sns=tw>

project architects. The gender distribution of the blog contributors is four female and three male contributors. This distribution does not surprise as the humanities are female-dominated fields (European Commission 2016, 26-29). Similarly, it does not strike that the main contributors on the technical side (and GitHub) are men.

Since the focus of the project does not lie on gender in the Homeric literature, the dissemination material of the project does not address gender sensitive topics in particular. The focus lies on multi-textuality of the Homeric texts. We could not find any material that does explicitly include gender aspects.

Highlight

Using GitHub for Research Data and other Resources

Originally GitHub has been built as an Open Source development platform to host and review code, manage projects, and build and share software with the worldwide developer community. With the advent of the Open Science movement, the platform is increasingly being used to share other resources such as research data or text documents as well. GitHub is a powerful Open Science tool as it includes functionalities to comment, review, manage, and discover contents as well as managing contributions by the community. In particular features enabling version control and branching of contents are useful and important mechanisms in context of a collaborative Open Science.

The HMT project uses GitHub not only to share its software code, but also archival data sets, code libraries, and documentation of how their archive is assembled. Other examples of projects using GitHub for sharing scientific documentation or open data files are listed on the GitHub website.

8.12 101 Innovations in Scholarly Communications

Table 58. Factsheet of the 101 Innovations in Scholarly Communications case

Factsheet	
Project Lead	Bianca Kramer and Jeroen Bosman, Utrecht University Library, Utrecht, Netherlands
Discipline	Information Science
Type	Citizen science/crowdsourcing project
Link	https://101innovations.wordpress.com/

Why?

101 Innovations in scholarly communication is a project that aims to analyse in detail research life-cycle phases and innovative tools that are used by researchers in each of the phases. Specifically, the purpose of the project was to investigate to what extent researchers are using the innovative communication tools compared to traditional ones and what impact these tools have on the research workflow.

Who?

Founders of the project Bianca Kramer and Jeroen Bosman from Utrecht University Library, Utrecht, Netherlands came up with an idea to tackle the questions such as: how the innovative tools impact research workflows and how they support a Good, Efficient and Open science (G-E-O model). These questions they addressed to researchers and people supporting research in different disciplines and different career stages.

What & How?

Dissemination activities range from the distribution of the tools database in Google Spreadsheets⁵⁶, the global survey⁵⁷ (i.e., was open from May 10, 2015 until February 10, 2016), interactive visualizations of survey results⁵⁸, collaboration with 108 partners (using their communication channels and mailing lists) to public blogs, social media, talks, webcasts and podcasts. One of the most interesting outputs is a snapshot of 101 tools visualized in a circle aligned to six research-lifecycle phases⁵⁹. To the dissemination outputs count also datasets and scripts^{60,61} as well as open peer reviewed scientific article and poster⁶².

When?

In late 2013 founders of the project came up with an idea to gather tools that researchers use in their research workflow. Dissemination started in 2014 when they went publicly with the google spreadsheet and invited researchers to add their tools. Around 200 tools were gathered very quickly; in January 2015 they published “the circle” with 101 most important innovative tools for scholarly communication.

The goal of the project was to use crowdsourcing for the database of innovative tools, so the dissemination was started in the very early stages of the project, after the first research life-cycle phase - De-

⁵⁶https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1KUMSeq_Pzp4KveZ7pb5rddcssk1XBTiLHniD0d3nDqo/edit#gid=1519702055

⁵⁷ <https://101innovations.files.wordpress.com/2016/02/101-innovations-survey-english.pdf>

⁵⁸ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1d2YSAmYGEw1WTMHk2Wfz-L155bjxT6eQk0772FJko8E/edit#gid=498287847>

⁵⁹ <http://innoscholcomm.silk.co/>

⁶⁰ <https://zenodo.org/record/49583#.WlibfVXhCpo>

⁶¹ <https://www.kaggle.com/bmkramer/101-innovations-research-tools-survey>

⁶² <https://f1000research.com/articles/5-692/v1>

sign. From the first dissemination activities, new opportunities and activities were created. In general, dissemination is noticeable after each research life-cycle phase.

Relation to Open Science

All dissemination outputs of the project are publicly available and licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) or Attribution-ShareAlike (CC BY-SA) license, and thus compatible with the Open Definition. Furthermore, published journal articles are open access.

The outcomes of the project can be used by libraries, research support, funders, but also by researchers themselves. Participants of the survey got immediate preliminary feedback from the survey. They could compare their usage of the tools with the average of their peers (i.e., for the six phases of the research cycle, a radar chart shows whether someone's tool usage is more traditional or more innovative than the average of their peer group).

Effort

The project is characterized with high quality reports, images, videos and blogs. The dissemination costs can be estimated as medium (< EUR 50,000). Worth mentioning is that part of the dissemination is conducted by 108 partners (mostly universities and publishers) and survey participants were not paid.

Impact

The global survey was designed to have a broader coverage including all countries, 7 different disciplines (derived from Scopus categorization) and researchers in different career stages. It was open for anyone to take, with no systematic control on who took it. The survey was available in 7 languages (English, Spanish, French, Chinese, Russian, Japanese and Arabic) and it was taken by 20,663 researchers, librarians, editors, publishers and other groups involved in research.

Impact: more than 600 tools are identified and gathered in a database which is publicly available. 101 tools with the most impact are visualized in an image ("the circle"), categorized based on six research life-cycle phases.

Gender

One of the co-founders of the project is a woman - Bianca Kramer from Utrecht University Library, Netherlands, who also plays an important role in the dissemination.

The global survey constructed within the project was intended to be as general as possible, without particular gender targeting. Participants of the global survey were not asked about their gender. No facts are found about the gender of the volunteers that contributed in the google spreadsheet. No explicit ambition is noticed regarding gender sensitive text and communication within the dissemination materials.

Highlight

Method: Image

By applying crowdsourcing it was possible to identify and gather more than 600 tools in a database, which is publicly available. 101 tools with the most impact are visualized in a diagram ("the circle"), categorized based on six research life-cycle phases (see **Error! Reference source not found.**). The image became very popular on social media; as a result it is widely known and as such has become the face of the project.

Figure 11 Collection of 101 innovative tools/platforms in various phases of the research cycle
 Source: Bosman & Kramer <https://innoscholcomm.silk.co/>. License: CC BY-SA

9. Appendix 2: Final Evaluation Reports for OpenUP Innovative Dissemination Pilots (WP6)

The seven pilot studies run under the sixth Work Package of the OpenUP project were successful and collected valuable input from the communities involved. Key stakeholders involved in the pilots were researchers, publishers, data providers, institutions, research projects, and general public stakeholders. The pilots contributed to raising awareness and increasing skills related to the tested open science approaches among the involved communities, and generated lessons learned and an evidence base on various aspects of the tested approaches. Lessons learned and insights about applicability of the tested approaches to a specific field and community as well as their impact on distinct research communities and researchers are gathered in the lessons learned section of the main report. We here reproduce the detailed pilot evaluation reports for the three pilots related to innovative dissemination.

9.1 A data journal for the Arts and Humanities (OpenUP pilot 3)

9.1.1 Introduction: Data publishing in the Humanities

Within the digital ecosystem the flow of information and innovative practices, such as data mining, data harvesting and commenting slowly transforms Humanities research. Research practices in the Humanities increasingly incorporate the use of digital resources and tools. As open access becomes a vital aspect of research dissemination and of the scholarly discourse in general, an increasing proportion of research results in the Humanities are published in an open way. Furthermore, besides publishing through traditional venues, such as journal and monographs in print or digital form, new forms of publishing are used by researchers (pre-prints, depositing datasets, writing scientific blogs) (Operas, 2018).

Openness permeates every aspect of the scholarly communication process; not only dissemination, but also reviewing and assessing research outputs. The concept of open peer review (OPR; defined and discussed in D3.4 (Görögh, 2018)) is an essential element of Open Science and closely intertwined with alternative forms of publishing, as it is connected to specific features of digital publishing in the Humanities (e.g. annotation technologies and commenting).

The pilot has a dual purpose: on the one hand, it describes the data sharing practices within Humanities research, and on the other hand, the study evaluates how quality assessment and (open) peer review can be applied to research data within this field of study. Based on existing e-Infrastructures and practices of Humanities research groups the pilot analyses and demonstrates the feasibility of a basic workflow that will combine the publication of data with commenting and reviewing systems. The research setting is provided by DARIAH-EU and DARIAH-DE, their extended network of Humanities research groups and by the research groups related to the Campus Labor at the University of Göttingen.

9.1.2 Methodology

The study builds on desk research based on reports and survey executed by DARIAH projects. DARIAH is a pan-European infrastructure for Arts and Humanities scholars working with computational methods. Besides supporting digital research, it puts an emphasis on teaching of digital research methods. DARIAH is also a network connecting several hundreds of scholars and dozens of research facilities, which provides digital tools for researchers and shares data as well as know-how. One of the priorities of DARIAH-EU is to build relationships and engage with communities about research and education based on practice or career level, and to identify user needs within those communities. DARIAH-DE, as an active participant of the DARIAH-EU network, contributes to the international research competitiveness and connectivity by developing a modern research infrastructure for the humanities and cultural sciences. Thus, the gathered information on user needs (DARIAH survey results), and the infrastructural development within the DARIAH-DE project provide the basis for the framework of the data Humanities data journal.

Other inputs for the study were provided by workshop results: 1. OpenUP workshop on open peer review “Open Peer Review hands on: alternative methods of evaluation in scholarly publishing” at the DARIAH annual event on 23 May 2018 in Paris, France, and 2. FOSTER/OPENUP joined training day on open peer review on 20 June 2018 in Göttingen, Germany.

As Digital Humanities (DH) has become an area of Humanities research where innovative tools, digital workflows and new methodologies based on collaborative and interdisciplinary work are employed, more attention is drawn in this field to the development and implementation of new principles and standards that ensure openness, interoperability and processability of scientific information. Therefore, researchers in the Digital Humanities Department at the University of Göttingen and members of the Campus Labor were asked to provide input in connection to data management and data sharing within their research practices.

9.1.3 What is data in the Humanities?

Due to the explosion in the creation and sharing of digital sources in multiple formats, several issues of data management and data exchange should be examined. These issues address the problems all Humanities research groups face in the strengthening European discourse of open data: the common translations of data, common vocabularies for describing data, the transparent process of data management, the legal and infrastructural issues of reuse of data and long-term data preservation. Data, in its more general sense, as something to be [measured](#), [collected](#), [reported](#), and [analyzed](#), is not a common concept in Humanities since most of Humanities content and research cannot be related to numbers and statistics (Konnikova, 2012). However, research data is as diverse as the disciplines that use them, and they can be defined, on broad terms, as the evidence used to inform or support research conclusions⁶³.

However, due to the increasing attention to the research processes and their underlying structures in science, data have become a common basic principle in scholarly discourse including the Humanities fields. It is hard to define research data in the context of Humanities. A definition offered by Schoch is: data in the humanities could be considered a digital, selective, machine-actionable construction of the object of humanistic inquiry. There are two basic types of data in the humanities: big data (relatively unstructured, messy and implicit, relatively large in volume, and varied in form) and smart data (semi-structured or structured, clean and explicit, as well as relatively small in volume and of limited heterogeneity) (Schoch, 2017). Due to the varied fields of study involved in Humanities, the contextualization of data is needed to understand research data management. Obviously, digital humanists would have a different take on what should be considered data and how to store than historians or archaeologists. Therefore, this pilot does not wish to untangle the extremely complex domain of Humanities data management. As the focus of the study centres more on publishing data rather than on data management services, the pilot is more concerned about the ways underlying data can be shared among researchers or published.

9.1.4 What is data publishing?

Publishing data has been defined as a process to make data as permanently available as possible on the Internet (Lawrence, 2011). However, the publication of data is not only making datasets available on the net, but it involves a service of checking the metadata and format of datasets (Callaghan, 2013). Formal data publication usually provides the data user with associated metadata, a persistence identifier for easy discoverability, and a platform for the dataset.

The data journal, defined by the RDA-WDS Publishing Data Workflows Working Group (WG), is a journal (invariably Open Access) that publishes data articles. The data journal usually provides templates for data description and offers researchers guidance on where to deposit and how to describe and

⁶³ <https://www.sheffield.ac.uk/library/rdm/whatisrdm>

present their data. Furthermore, the data article has the primary aim of providing a formal route to data-sharing. It is the carrier of information on the standards of curation, formatting, availability, persistence or peer review of the dataset (Austin, 2017).

9.1.5 Data sharing

Schöpfel and Prost conducted a campus-wide survey on data management, data reuse and data sharing issues in 2015. The anonymous online questionnaire, disseminated within the whole research community on the social sciences and humanities campus (1,800 persons), did not have a high response rate (receiving 270 responses - 15% of the whole sample). The survey provides an insight into the attitudes of students, scholars, research management administrators toward open data and data sharing.

Most respondents (64%) do not share their research data with colleagues or other people. Nobody, except themselves, have access to their data files. Only 34% share data with their colleagues and/or members of their research team, and only 5% share them with a wider audience, in the strict sense of an open data approach. Few replied to the question about the reuse of data produced by other researchers (58%), and even fewer (38%, i.e. 22% of the whole sample) said that they had already downloaded this kind of scientific output. Also, very few answered that they were not interested or motivated to reuse other researchers' data. One third (38%) simply were (are) not aware of this opportunity and way of doing science.

The general willingness to deposit and share their data was also tested. About 40% of the respondents express a positive opinion about data sharing. Either they have already deposited their data in a repository (16%) or they intend to do so in the future (25%). 30% admit that they were not aware of this possibility.

Another third (29%) clearly say that they never deposited their research data in the past and that they have no intention of doing so in the future. A deposit in a data repository is no option for five reasons: sensitive and confidential data, risk of plagiarism, workload, data illegibility ("nobody would understand my raw data") and intellectual property. This rejection of data sharing significantly decreases when it comes to the question of publishing data along with an article, i.e. when data sharing is incentive or obligatory. 44% of the respondents state that they have already published data together with an article, and 31% announce that they intend to do so in the future while 18% admit that they simply did not know about this possibility.

Regarding the kind of data they would share, only 12% clearly state that they will not deposit or share their research results in this way. 37% underline that they would share those data asked for by their peers while others say that they would deposit data produced in collaborative research projects (33%) or with public funding (25%). As for the infrastructure they would use for depositing data, most of the researchers indicated the use of international data repositories (47%) as a primary preference, followed by local servers hosted by the laboratory, i.e. the research institute (39%). National (35%) or campus-wide platforms (31%) are less preferred. In other words, this sample is more interested in impact and visibility (international repository) and disciplinary specificity (laboratory) than in a multidisciplinary, national or institutional solution.

A web-based survey conducted by the Digital Methods and Practices Observatory (DiMPO), a working group under VCC2 of the DARIAH research infrastructure (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities)⁶⁴ asked European researchers (2177 respondents) about their scholarly practices and digital needs in the arts and humanities.

The results show similarity with the Schöpfel survey. A majority of the respondents (9/10) indicated that they use a word processor for storage and management of research assets. Three out of five respondents stated they use spreadsheets, while about one third said they use database management

⁶⁴ <https://zenodo.org/record/260101#.W3aPpLpuLQO>

systems or note-taking and bibliographic citation management applications. Only one out of seven presently use web-based content management systems (CMS) to store and manage research assets.

As opposed to their actual practices of sharing data, researchers rated the findability and access to existing digital research resources or data as the most important (scores 9.5/10). A slightly lower score of 9 was granted to digitization of research resources or data currently not in digital form by three out of four respondents. Two other needs, improved findability and access to digital tools or software, and networking with other researchers, research groups and institutions, share third place with a score exceeding 7 by more than three out of four respondents.

9.1.6 Barriers to data sharing in the Humanities

There are numerous barriers researchers encounter in data exchange processes. One of the main obstacles is the generally closed world of scientific discourse in the Humanities. Much of the work in European Humanities research is not visible. The disperse research communities often fail to connect to one another because of the language barriers. Humanities scholars very often publish in their national languages, and the trend is to continue doing so in the future. Europe lacks an integrated database of published journals in various national languages. A database of this kind could be a sort of 'who's who' within a particular field of research.

Another barrier relates to the actual research data. Due to lack of standards and common guidelines in data managements, it is very difficult to connect data. There are initiatives on a EU level, which work toward a more unified Humanities research landscape. CLARIN, the Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure, is focused on integrating language data across Europe. DARIAH, the Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and the Humanities, is more focused on increasing the visibility at the European level of national research related to cultural heritage, digital arts, etc. These two projects provide a positive direction of development in this field. Both projects try to fill in the gaps where no data exists and try to connect data where it does exist but lives a life of its own in an unconnected place.

Since there is a global trend towards inter-, multi-, and transdisciplinarity, the Humanities research field should be encouraged to participate in data exchange processes across research domains⁶⁵.

9.1.7 Current data sharing standards

The basic principle behind developing standards for sharing research data is the purpose of publication of scientific information is to move science forward. In this sense, an author's obligation is not only to release data to verify or replicate published findings, but also to provide them in a form for reuse. Thus, standards maximize the value of scientific findings to the community (National Research Council, 2003).

9.1.8 FAIR principles

The FAIR guiding principles for research data stewardship (findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability) look set to become a cornerstone of research in many disciplines, and they are being incorporated into Humanities discourse on research data as well. FAIR refers to a set of guiding principles that support increasing reusability, via many different implementations. They are sometimes incorrectly referred to as a 'standard', allowing many different approaches to rendering data and services Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, to serve the ultimate goal: the reuse of valuable research objects (Mons, 2017).

European policies on research data are now aligned to the FAIR principles, and they are expressed in science-centric language, not using broad expressions applicable both to science and arts. This causes the arts and humanities researchers to feel marginalized and disengaged (Kotar, 2018).

⁶⁵ <https://sciencenode.org/feature/digital-humanities-overcoming-barriers-data-sharing.php>

9.1.9 Data Citation Principles

Data citation, like the citation of other evidence and sources, is good research practice and is part of the scholarly ecosystem supporting data reuse. The Data Citation Principles⁶⁶ cover purpose, function and attributes of citations. These principles recognize the dual necessity of creating citation practices that are both understandable by humans and machine-actionable. Several of these principles actually pertain to data publishing, like:

- Importance: data should be considered legitimate, citable products of research. Data citations should be accorded the same importance in the scholarly record as citations of other research objects, such as publications.
- Access: Data citations should facilitate access to the data themselves and to such associated metadata, documentation, code, and other materials, as are necessary for both humans and machines to make informed use of the referenced data.
- Persistence: Unique identifiers, and metadata describing the data, and its disposition, should persist - even beyond the lifespan of the data they describe.
- Interoperability and Flexibility: Data citation methods should be sufficiently flexible to accommodate the variant practices among communities but should not differ so much that they compromise interoperability of data citation practices across communities.

Other standards which are relevant for data publishing and reuse include DC (Dublin Core), EDM (European data model) and EAD (Encoding archival description).

9.1.10 Best practices

Within the context of this pilot, we have examined projects that can serve as best practices for publishing data and building an infrastructure for advancing data sharing. There are initiatives focusing on widening the access to data through the development of digital archives that are reusable in an open access framework. Since the EC supports research infrastructure (RI) developments in the Humanities with special attention to the field of Digital Humanities, there are several projects, such as DARIAH ERIC⁶⁷, DIGILAB⁶⁸, KPLEX⁶⁹ projects, that have the agenda of creating RIs, including the development of networks of facilities and resources and services offered to research communities to support their work.

These initiatives help us defining the context, elements and work process for developing and implementing a data journal. Some of the best examples of data publishing projects include HumaReC,⁷⁰ a Swiss National Foundation Project, which aims at developing a certified and continuous data publishing digital research in the Humanities (Clivaz, 2017). The established book publishing, the traditional Humanistic way of disseminating research results, has been challenged by the a completely new paradigm by transforming research through digital writing material. New methods of dissemination have surfaced in the form of videos, draft papers, social media posts, short syntheses of datasets in blogs before the research is completed and peer-reviewed (Schulthess, 2017). The project sets out to observe the changes happening in Digital Humanities research by continuously publishing their data related to the project research on an open platform: three publication formats were chosen for data dissemination: (1) a virtual research environment with ISSN where all the published material associated with the project is collected, (2) a research blog on the development of the project, and (3) an open access web-book summarizing the research in a narrative. These results will provide first-hand experience on disseminating research data through open channels of communication and on the community-based commenting and review practices.

⁶⁶ Data Citation Synthesis Group: Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles. Martone M. (ed.) San Diego CA: FORCE11; 2014 [<https://www.force11.org/group/joint-declaration-data-citation-principles-final>].

⁶⁷ <https://ehri-project.eu/launching-dariah-eric-arts-and-humanities-go-digital>

⁶⁸ <http://www.e-rihs.eu/ercim-news-digital-humanities/>

⁶⁹ <https://kplex-project.eu/>

⁷⁰ <https://humarec.org/>

Another example is project PARTHENOS⁷¹ that focuses effort more on improving and maximizing access to and the reuse of research data through the development of Humanities data template. The development of a PARTHENOS data management plan which builds on the Horizon2020 DMP template aims at addressing the domain-specific procedures and practices within the humanities, taking into consideration standards and guidelines used in data management that are relevant for PARTHENOS specific research communities. Besides standardization in the areas of documentation of primary data and sources, reference resources and procedures and protocols, tasks in the project address interoperability and semantics through defining a common semantic framework, and designing resource discovery. The ultimate goal in PARTHENOS is to define the technical development of the tools and services that are required to create the desired trans-humanities research infrastructure. The project results here provide an excellent example for building a cross-disciplinary environment to enable humanities researchers to have access to data, tools and services based on common policies, guidelines and standards (Bassett, 2017).

OPERAS⁷² provides pan-European infrastructure and services for open access to social science and humanities research requires widespread coordination and support, as well as funding from supporting countries. This can best be achieved by application to the Roadmap of the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) which supports the development and implementation of mature pan-European research infrastructures. Within the recently published Operas White Paper the importance of a common operational framework for digital publishing is acknowledged. Furthermore, it is emphasized that the effective implementation of common standards is highly depended upon stakeholders' increased awareness and commitment towards more effective ways of conducting, presenting and communicating research. The OPERAS network supports and wishes to coordinate an initiative for the introduction of publishing standards, in the SSH and beyond. A sustainable approach for the introduction of operational and technical standards for electronic publishing should take into account discipline-specific standards, user needs and domain specific research and publishing workflows (Operas, 2018).

9.1.11 Data journal framework and workflows

The development of a data journal framework involves a description of the communication flow and a breakdown of this process into single steps. The data journal framework should include the following attributes:

- the assignment of persistent identifiers (PIDs) to datasets,
- peer review of data
- metadata information and technical check
- links to related outputs (journal articles)
- facilitation of data citation
- standards compliance
- discoverability (indexing of the data).

The RDA-WDS Publishing Data Workflows Working Group (WG) has developed a data publication process (Figure 11) which shows the double route of data publishing through repositories and data journals. These two methods of publishing are interlinked since the formal publication of data sets in a data journal usually requires the deposit of data sets in a repository. Both ways of data sharing adhere to specific sets of standards to ensure discoverability and reuse of the datasets. However, the review process may differ. The submission to a repository is reviewed from a variety of perspectives depending on the policies and practices of the repository including formatting issues, content, metadata or other technical details and version control of the data set. The data journals are similar to the traditional research journal, thus besides the formal peer review of the validity of the data, the dissemination of the datasets is included in their communication processes. Reviewers have pre-publication ac-

⁷¹ <http://www.parthenos-project.eu/>

⁷² <https://operas.hypotheses.org/>

cess to the datasets, so it is important that the data journals and the repositories adhere to the same standards of processing data and workflow coordination (Austin, 2017).

Figure 12 Research data publication workflow.

Source: Austin, C.C., Bloom, T., Dallmeier-Tiessen, S. et al. (2017). *Int J Digit Libr* 18: 77.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00799-016-0178-2>

There are similarities between the peer review of an article and the peer review of data, but data review includes more issues to manage. Research datasets can be really complex, multifaceted information objects. Some datasets are constantly changing and being added to over time, so version controlling is a necessary feature added to the data sets. Review of data should involve the checking and evaluation of the methodology of the data collection, the examination of the software code used to process the data (Carpenter, 2017). Therefore, data peer review is conducted by invited domain experts external to the data journal (e.g. RIO journals). With the rise of open or post-publication peer review, some data journals are also inviting the wider community to participate in the publication process.

The data publishing workflow should provide information about the types of data accepted for publication, the roles of involved stakeholders including authors' guidelines and requirements of publishing, rules of the review process (options and rules of open peer review), standards used, identifiers accepted and their connection (linking of identifiers, such as ISNI, VIAF, GND with ORCID).

9.1.12 Issues to be solved: workshop results

OpenUP organized two events where the issue of data sharing was discussed in detail and the feedback from the representatives from Humanities communities shared: a workshop at the DARIAH annual event in 2018 and the OPENUP/FOSTER joined training workshop.

During the small group discussion section of the workshop the topic of data sharing and data availability was examined more in-depth. Participants were given a poster on which they could record examples of good practice, barriers and challenges to implementation, and (based on these barriers) what actions should be taken, by whom. The group rotated so that each group moved on to evaluate and validate the findings of the other groups. They had the option of adding any points they feel were not covered by the previous group. We received valuable input from researchers and publishers.

Participants listed the following challenges and barriers that hinder the uptake of data sharing and data publishing:

- some disciplines are less willing to share materials than others,
- unclear intellectual property rules and licensing,
- data ownership issues,
- technical aspects of linking research outputs,
- lack of incentives to do the extra work (reformatting, anonymizing, making datasets platform ready).

The actions needed to solve these issues recommended by the workshop participants are the following:

- raising awareness of licensing option, data ownership issues, intellectual property issues,
- developing and implementing data documentation processes,
- including steps on data curation in the regular research workflow.

9.1.13 Solutions and examples

Registered Reports, an increasingly required step in the research workflow in social psychology and in certain fields of life sciences, may contribute to open data sharing. Registering the research procedure before the actual data collection makes explicit how the research is conducted and make all the relevant materials and data available to facilitate reanalysis, reuse, and replication. A special issue of the journal *Social Psychology* in 2014 presented 15 articles with replications of important results in social psychology, which included Registered Reports in their research and publishing process. All these articles demonstrated that the original proposals, anonymized data, and study materials are registered and available at the Open Science Framework (OSF⁷³). Furthermore, each article earned badges acknowledging pre-registration, open data, and open materials and the badges and links to the OSF projects appear in the acknowledgments section of each article (Nosek, 2014). Thus, Registered Reports practices provide authors the workflow how to include data in the publishing procedure and the incentive to share data and materials with the research communities.

The Campus Laboratory DCA at the University of Göttingen is an interdisciplinary centre for research on innovative digital methods in the Humanities and Social Sciences with a focus on data analytics. Data on the research workflows collected from the projects and institutes belonging to the Campus Lab DCA and infrastructure shed light on Humanities data management and curation practices. Information gained within the data collection process demonstrates that

- the data these Humanities projects work with are greatly varied,
- the storage and long-term archiving is usually solved internally within the project either on the institute's server, computer or the department's cloud service,
- data sharing is managed mainly within the closed research environment e.g. through a virtual drive which can be accessed by request (www.landeshgeschichte.uni-goettingen.de/chausseen).

9.1.14 Lessons Learned

These practices demonstrate the lack of standardized workflows for data curation, sharing and publishing. Humanities data management practices at the University of Göttingen demonstrate a varied picture with various degree of openness in regard to archiving and sharing data within the research groups and with external researchers. Humanities projects and departments could take advantage of the institutional repository infrastructure or the developing DARIAH data repository services where standardized data templates, workflows and added quality assurances tools could provide a more consistent view on data publishing across the different disciplines in Humanities. Implementation of standards and guidelines for managing research data would definitely support a more common view on data sharing and data availability within Humanities projects. In many cases the tools are given for

⁷³ <http://osf.io/>

data publishing (e.g. psycholinguists are using a platform for data analysis which allows the publishing of the description of the data set, a data paper in a push of a button), however the awareness around the benefits and value of sharing research data is not part of their research flow. Humanities data publishing will be more prominent as awareness is increased among researchers on data management and data discoverability issues.

9.1.15 References

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9.2 Transferring the research lifecycle to the web via Open Online Research (OpenUP pilot 4)

9.2.1 Introduction

In this pilot, we addressed the question whether data analysis and data collection in qualitative research can be transferred to open online groups, in which potentially both academics and non-academics can participate. A special focus lied on mechanisms to reach out to and engage citizens in qualitative research processes. Our aim was to transfer the data-analysis and data collection parts of the research lifecycle to the web. To this end, we developed dedicated software called OpenOnlineResearch (OOR)⁷⁴ further. Figures 13 and 14 below show two of the main pages in OOR. Figure 13 shows the landing page and one exemplary project “interpreting depression”. Figure 14 shows the two main types of activities participants can engage in now: upload data or interpret data.

In Pilot 4 we successfully tested and further developed OOR. In particular, we tested the applicability of this online solution to involve citizens in qualitative research. The goal was to gain further insight into working practices and address current challenges/gaps of open online collaboration approaches applied to qualitative research.

OOR builds on prototypes developed earlier at the University of Amsterdam⁷⁵. At that point, the prototypes were geared to academic participants who already had some experience with similar tools. In OpenUP we worked to make the software easier to use, which allowed to involve citizens that were not experienced in research or using the tool. More precise descriptions of the earlier steps of the OOR development can be found in the intermediate report⁷⁶.

In a second step, it was foreseen to engage citizens through the Coursera⁷⁷ online course platform. The initial plan to create the first Open Online Research in Coursera, however, turned out not to be practical. Below we detail why we changed for Coursera to the Zooniverse citizen science platform. Due to this switch, the final test round with the Zooniverse community could not be concluded during the second pilot implementation phase. However, an additional thorough small-scale test round involving our extended team has been done, and we performed a small test at the demo session at the OpenUP Final Conference⁷⁸. The final test with the Zooniverse community is scheduled for the end of 2018. The final test is meant to determine the scalability of the method. The principles of the method and tool are tested in OpenUP. Throughout the pilot we attended to diversity and inclusion. We aimed at including citizens with different national, cultural, class, race, age and gender backgrounds.

⁷⁴ Login <http://mooruva.staging.vellance.net/> (htaccess):

User: openup

Pass: CzTd4xjrGuuawbp92tGntKh

⁷⁵ Christian, C., Gerben, G., JC, J. C., LR, L. R., Lianne, L., Stoopendaal, A., ... & Hege, H. (2016, January). Open online research: Developing software and method for collaborative interpretation. In *Forum Qualitative Sozialforschung* (Vol. 17, No. 3).

⁷⁶ Vignoli et al. 2017, Deliverable D6.2: Interim Use Case Evaluation Report. pp. 17 ff. http://openup-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/01/OpenUP_D6.2_Interim-Use-Case-Evaluation-Report.pdf

⁷⁷ <https://www.coursera.org/>

⁷⁸ <http://openup-h2020.eu/openup-final-conference/>

Figure 13 Screenshot of the further developed OpenOnlineResearch tool.

9.2.2 Software tests in OpenUP

The tests have been reported about earlier⁷⁹. In summary: we have performed three tests with team members and non-team members (uninitiated and untrained students from different disciplines plus non-academic and academic members of our network) before 2018.

In 2018, following further improvement of the tool, we had a software test with the extended team. In this test we both assessed the workings of the functionalities, the specific needs for (a minimum of) instructions and the CMS and output capacities so far. 5 different users went from log-in to interpretation to stacking repeatedly. All steps were analysed, and potential improvements were discussed. The test revealed no major flaws.

Additionally, we have interactively demonstrated and tested the tool at the final OpenUP conference. We invited conference participants to use the interpretation features of OOR, visually observe the use of it, and asked them about usability, instructions and meaning of the interpretations given. Six participants have gone through the software and performed the main operations. It turned out that users understand the flow and meaning of the software swiftly and are able to produce meaningful content. It also turned out that we omitted a small number of instructions. The test also triggered participants

⁷⁹ Vignoli et al. 2017, Deliverable D6.2: Interim Use Case Evaluation Report. pp. 17 ff. http://openup-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/01/OpenUP_D6.2_Interim-Use-Case-Evaluation-Report.pdf

to think about the applicability of the tool. For example: one participant suggested to try the tool for peer-review.

The results of the test rounds confirmed that online applications such as the OOR tool enable citizens to gather and analyse data online and openly by means of a model investing in social moderation. The test round was assisted by a team of academics and the previously mentioned tailor-made software.

9.2.3 OOR: From Coursera to Zooniverse

While we were rather advanced with the Coursera course approach, we nonetheless decided to switch from Coursera to Zooniverse. This change was driven by two considerations. First of all, Coursera is becoming more commercial which forms an obstacle to participation. UVA runs several courses on Coursera and have made some discouraging experiences related to this development. Second, the need for training in Coursera became less pronounced since the OOR software testing enabled a much easier to use design as a standalone tool. Finally, we produced a number of online tutorials at our disposition for participants who desire methodological training about OOR.

Zooniverse⁸⁰ is the world largest citizen science platform with about 1 million users. It contains dozens of citizen science projects, largely in the area of the natural sciences, partly in behavioural science (psychology) and humanities (mainly history and translation of handwriting). The number of participants in separate Zooniverse research projects is mostly about one to three thousand. The total number of volunteer participants is roughly one million⁸¹.

Since early 2018 we exchanged information with Zooniverse. They were interested the way our tool enables collaboration since current Zooniverse projects are largely based on distributed tasks rather than direct collaboration between citizens. The Zooniverse software does not enable direct collaboration yet. The current platform and projects are often about visual data, while OOR contains a methodology for textual data. Zooniverse were also interested in the interpretive approach of OOR, which is novel and still underdeveloped in the field of citizen science. OOR has developed an approach to include diverse perspectives which is different from Zooniverse and other citizen science platforms. In short, the switch from Coursera to Zooniverse confirmed that our approach and tool are promising and opened new possibilities for OOR to reach out to citizens.

Collaboration with Zooniverse has helped us to further develop and simplified the OOR tool, since it further pressured us to design for a largely unknown and diverse group of participants. Apart from data output, most parts of the software are developed and tested.

⁸⁰ <https://www.zooniverse.org/>

⁸¹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Zooniverse>

Figure 14 Screenshot of the input screen in the OpenOnlineResearch tool

9.2.4 After OpenUp

After OpenUp and without the use of OpenUp funding, we will perform a test in Zooniverse. The test will start late 2018 and run for 1 to 4 weeks, depending on participation. We expect early large-scale participation which would mean a test period of a week.

The Zooniverse test will focus on scaling up and the pitfalls we encounter when scaling up. We have three methods to evaluate the final test.

1. Back-end data analysis: Which proportions of participants contribute observations, generate interpretations, stack interpretation, chat with each other, adjust interpretations etc?
2. Analysis of the quality: Researchers compare the contributions to existing research.
3. Survey to participants: After their contribution has ended, participants receive an invitation for a survey about: user experience, learning outcomes, experience of collaboration, empowerment. In the analysis of the survey data, specific attention will be given to gender, class and regional differences.

9.2.5 Lessons Learned

Within OpenUP, Pilot 4 demonstrates that open online interpretation of qualitative data is feasible and that yet unused parts of the research cycle can be opened to wider ranges of collaborators both within and outside academia.

The results of the testing confirmed that the Open Online Research (OOR) tool enables online collaborative interpretation. Three iterations of the tool have been tested by various groups of participants (5-40 people). A further test falls outside the reporting period but it builds on the insights from the tests done in the frame of OpenUP.

More precisely we learned that a simple tool, without the need for detailed instruction, is feasible. We also learned that the input of scientists is still needed for the formulation of sound research questions and instructions. We have also seen that online collaboration needs moderation (either technically or by humans) to settle differences. However, we found that conflicts were rare and that participants were willing to collaborate in most cases.

The outcomes of this pilot are feeding into future developments in open science in two ways. First, the collaboration with Zooniverse is continuing and might lead to either an integration of OOR methodology in Zooniverse or to a strengthening of OOR. Second, the continuity is safeguarded by new funding appointed by the University of Amsterdam. Based on the progress made within OpenUP, the UvA was willing to invest into the development of service package for OOR. While OOR is designed to be open and freely available, certain users might have more elaborate needs when using the tool. The need for services is assessed with the funding. In short, OOR is evolving beyond OpenUP.

9.3 Addressing & reaching businesses and the public with research output (OpenUP pilot 5)

9.3.1 Introduction

The goal of the fifth OpenUP pilot study was to analyse and test how disseminated research results can be made more interesting, appealing, and usable for target audiences beyond the research community. In this pilot we particularly addressed dissemination to **businesses** and the **general public**.

In context of Task 4.4 we interviewed 7 science communication experts (4 male, 3 female) to define requirements and expectations by these targeted audiences. In addition, we consulted one of the community contacts of the previously involved SmarterTogether⁸² project, who was responsible for project communication. Based upon the feedback gathered, we created guidelines and recommendations for researchers who want to communicate their research to target audiences beyond academia.

In a second step these guidelines were tested by a research project in the **Energy research** area (**ReFlex**, a European smart grids project⁸³). Based on the provided recommendations and guidelines, the research community re-shaped and evaluated their dissemination strategy and produced targeted dissemination content tailored to its stakeholders. Feedback was collected in an informal discussion and an interview with 3 female and one male interviewees. They were people working directly with project dissemination. The collected feedback on their experiences in applying the guidelines is reported below.

The feedback from the ReFlex project gave us very valuable input to improve the guidelines. In particular we added one additional step regarding monitoring and implementing the dissemination strategy during the project runtime. The guidelines are currently being updated addressing the feedback received and will be provided on the OpenUP Hub⁸⁴ very soon.

⁸² <https://www.smartertogether.at/>

⁸³ <http://reflex-smartgrid.eu/>

⁸⁴ <https://www.openuphub.eu/>

9.3.2 Testing and feedback from ReFlex project

The main evaluation of Pilot 5 consisted of a qualitative part:

- Test the communication guidelines produced in Task 4.4 in the ReFlex project (the updated and final version of the recommendations is included in the Appendix)
- Dissemination of research content by the ReFlex project targeting businesses and the general public according to the OpenUP guidelines
- Gather feedback on the tested guidelines & improve them according to feedback

In March 2018 the ReFlex project agreed to become the new cooperation partner for the evaluation phase of the fifth OpenUP pilot study. During the period from April to June 2018 four individuals from ReFlex, who were in charge of the project's communication task, tested the guidelines in context of the dissemination activities of their project. Due to the late replacement of the SmarterTogether project, which dropped out from the cooperation early 2018, it was not possible to apply and test the guidelines more extensively.

Qualitative feedback on the ReFlex project's experiences was gathered from three community contacts in an interview. The interview was structured by 5 main guiding questions (below represented in italic). We gathered information about their general experience during the testing of the OpenUP guidelines as well as on the suitability of content and structure of the guidelines. Finally, we also asked their opinion on what could be improved in the current version of the guidelines. Additional feedback that was provided by one of the SmarterTogether contacts during the creation phase of the guidelines was considered as well.

Question 1: In general, how was your experience during the testing of the OpenUP guidelines?

In general, feedback was positive. The community contacts confirmed that the guidelines provided good support for setting up a structured dissemination and communication plan. The guidelines were helpful to assess and revise the project's dissemination strategy. In particular the **single steps and guiding questions** provided a good orientation and check for shaping the dissemination strategy and make it more target audience focused. The **expert tips**, however, were not perceived to be that useful. Feedback suggested that in particular the expert tips for businesses are in need of improvement.

The contacts told us that they liked the structured approach: it was helpful for them even if they already had a dissemination strategy at the time of the testing. It helped them to see what needs to be considered for the overall communication strategy planning and the later steps.

Finally, the community contacts confirmed that the guidelines are useful to shape/define a communication strategy. However, they stressed that they are not so useful/not sufficient to compose the final communication message itself. They provide orientation but not a real guidance about how the final communication message or media should actually look like.

One of the community contacts reported that she used the guidelines for another project as well. With the help of the guidelines, she was able to set up a communication plan for a conference in 15 minutes. This suggests that the guidelines are easy to use and well applicable to other contexts as well.

Question 2: Were the guidelines useful to better define your dissemination strategy towards addressing businesses and/or the general public?

In the case of the ReFlex project, the guidelines were not that useful to better define their target audiences because these were already well defined before. In the beginning of the project they had a communication plan, which was not target group specific at first. The target groups crystallised only during the first phase of the project (the project runs for one year). However, the community contacts confirmed that the guidelines would have been useful for this purpose if they had not already undergone this process. During the first project year they posed themselves similar questions to define their target audiences, and the guidelines would have supported this process.

Another positive effect of the guidelines was that at the beginning of the project they did not compose target audience specific tweets. This changed after they used the OpenUP guidelines.

The community contacts reported that they had difficulties in matching the two main target groups in the guidelines (businesses and general public) with their own target group definitions. In the ReFlex project communication to the general public is a clear dissemination goal; this was not an issue. However, businesses are not part of their targeted audiences. Instead, they are targeting **energy experts** as well as **local authorities/municipalities**. At the beginning it was not really clear for them which recommendations to follow for those target groups. From the description that we provided, it was not clear to them which target groups we had in mind when we drafted the recommendations. From the guidelines they understood that we divided the recommendations into expert (businesses) and non-expert audiences (general public). From the ReFlex project's experience, however, municipalities lie between expert and non-expert target groups (i.e. semi-experts). Also, the general public is a crucial customer for those target groups (e.g. communication for cities).

Earlier feedback provided by one of the communication contacts of the SmarterTogether project also suggested that the terminology is not necessarily straightforward. Next to small and medium businesses in the Energy area and members of the general public, local authorities and municipalities were also key audiences of the project. However, municipalities were mainly stakeholders of the project, and not so much target groups for communication. Feedback suggested that it is important to differentiate between stakeholders and target groups, and that both have varying implications for the communication strategy. Following to this comment we decided to stick to the target group terminology.

Feedback from the ReFlex project contacts suggested that the information regarding **general public** provided in the guidelines was more conclusive. However, the **businesses** target audience did not fit well with the audiences targeted by the ReFlex project. Businesses are experts with a very specific background which does not necessarily fit other, not business-oriented audiences that are also targeted in European research projects. The division into these two main target groups is rather arbitrary and cannot necessarily be applied to other specific target groups. From the beginning, we did not aim to develop overarching communication guidelines. However, the testing showed that more flexible guidelines including more target groups would be useful.

We decided to keep the differentiation between businesses and general public target audiences as this was what we defined in the Description of Action. However, already the dialogues with the science communication experts suggested that there are other target groups as well, and that they do not fit in the schema that we provided.

Question 3: Are the 4 steps well-chosen and in a logical order?

As reported above, the four steps were perceived to be very useful for planning the dissemination strategy. The community contacts commented that the steps are not necessarily part of a linear process. Defining objectives, target groups and key messages are clearly interconnected steps and can be iterative.

What they suggested was missing is a **final step on how to implement the guidelines during the project runtime**. The guidelines did not give advice on how to plan and implement a process to make sure that dissemination is being done in parallel to the project execution. Having this in place as well as to assign responsibilities are key criteria for a successful implementation of dissemination during the project runtime. It can also be a circular process, in which the previously defined objectives, key messages etc. are being assessed and refined during the project.

Question 4: Is the format of the written guidelines and the overview table appropriate? Which one was more useful for you?

The community contacts said that they mostly used the provided overview table. The table is written similarly to a checklist, which is very useful. The table summarises the key elements very well.

The length of the guidelines was perceived as good. The written text is less well suitable to have a ordered and quick guidance. This clearly gave us the confirmation that we needed to work further on the overview table as it is the better format to work with.

In the **overview table**, more background information would have been useful in some cases. More information is contained in the text document; however, it is not straightforward to look it up. Some sentences in the overview table were too short and not really helpful.

The **objectives** were the most useful for the ReFlex project, followed by the **guiding questions**. The **expert tips**, however, can be improved. Especially for the business target group they are not very helpful (they lack clarity and are not well applicable).

Question 5: Where do you see room for improvement?

Additional feedback from the ReFlex contacts gave us some hints about content and restructuring possibilities. An input was that **trans-disciplinary questions** are also often a challenge; they are not included in the guidelines. Also, **policy makers and other target groups**, which do not fit in the provided schema are missing, respectively it was not really easy to assign other target groups to this schema.

Practice examples are missing in the guidelines but would be really useful.

An alternative idea to make an infographic of the guidelines that was suggested by one of the contacts is to depict a linear process of the four steps with arrows in between.

Suggestions for the additional 5th step: The community contacts suggest that if one of the project partners is responsible for the dissemination and communications WP and the appointed person is engaged, it works. However, during the project runtime it is not only important to define key messages. It is also crucial to define who is in charge for communicating the messages. Who communicates with whom? Is it the same person, or are there various contact persons/persons responsible for communication? This might differ in the various project phases. This should also be considered in the planning phase.

Another point is the definition of communication phases: how regularly should communication happen during the project. Continuity of communication is essential for a good project communication (sustainability). Another important point during the project execution is to reflect and assess if the communicated messages fit the audience, the medium, etc.

9.3.3 Impact of ReFlex project's Twitter Activity and Reached Target Groups

The second part of the Pilot 5 evaluation consisted of a quantitative analysis of the achieved impact metrics of the project's Twitter channel and a qualitative analysis of the reached target groups. The goal was to explore if Altmetrics can be used as a meaningful indicator for assessing impact in specific stakeholder groups. In particular, we wanted to test if additional information about the reached target groups can be extracted by means of Altmetrics to answer the question if the alternative dissemination methodology applied helped making the research outputs more interesting, appealing, and re-usable.

Due to the delay caused by the drop-out of the Smarter Together community from the collaboration with OpenUP, it was not possible to analyse the impact of the composed tweets for a long enough period of time to allow meaningful conclusions. The ReFlex project only joined the pilot study in March 2018 and started testing the guidelines in April 2018. The project's main interactive online communication channel to reach out to the general public is their Twitter channel⁸⁵. During the guidelines testing period (i.e. from April to June 2018) they composed only five tweets on Twitter and had a rather modest impact. The two tweets with the most interactions had 3 re-tweets and 2-4 likes.

A comparison with the tweets sent previously to the OpenUP guidelines testing phase does not allow any conclusions about the success of the adapted communication strategy. The tweeting activity of the ReFlex project's Twitter account started in June 2017. Only two of the 5 tweets composed during the testing phase had a somewhat greater impact compared to the other tweets. However, since the num-

⁸⁵ <https://twitter.com/reflexsmartgrid>

ber of tweets, re-tweets and likes is still very low, it is not a relevant increase of impact. To be able to evaluate the success of the applied OpenUP guidelines in terms of increased impact, it would be necessary to observe the project over a longer period of time.

The qualitative analysis of the reached target groups was done by manually looking at the profile picture, the short text (incl. hash-tags) included in the Twitter profiles, and the history of tweets of the individual accounts from which the re-tweets and likes were made. The analysis of the Twitter profiles from the two most successful tweets shows the following distribution of accounts re-tweeting or liking the tweets:

- [Tweet from 21st of May 2018](#) (3 re-tweets, 4 likes)
 - 3 individuals with clear interests in research topics; 1 female, 1 male, 1 unknown
 - 2 individuals with other/not clearly attributable interests; 1 male, 1 unknown
 - 1 real estate developer
- [Tweet from 6th of June 2018](#) (3 re-tweets, 2 likes)
 - 3 individuals with other/not clearly attributable interests; 2 male, 1 unknown (female?)
 - 2 non-public accounts (no information available)

Looking at these results it is immediately clear that it is not an easy task to determine the reached target groups. For one, the information that one can deduct from the Twitter accounts is limited and, in some cases, not evidently pointing to one target group or the other. Only one of the cases above, the real estate developer account, was evidently belonging to the businesses target group. Some accounts had clear references to research topics in their profile descriptions. We could deduct that those individuals either are researchers or citizens with particular interest in research topics. However, the other individual accounts did not contain any clear reference allowing us to assign them to any specific target group.

9.3.4 Thoughts about analysing the reached target groups via Twitter

By looking at the Twitter profiles and the tweets of individual accounts, it is not always evident to which target group the reached individual belongs. For instance, even if the accounts clearly included references to interests in research topics in the profile description text, the tweets and re-tweets from their Twitter history did also refer to other topics such as politics. Accounts of individuals can be used very personally, professionally or both. This makes it difficult to draw conclusions about the stakeholder or target group an individual belongs to.

An additional difficulty are fake accounts (in fact, one of the individual accounts was marked by Twitter as restricted due to suspicious activities) and private accounts without a public profile. Determining the reached target audience is highly depending on contextual information. If this information is not provided or restricted, it is not possible to make any deductions in terms of target groups reached.

An additional challenge is scalability. Due to the low number of tweets we did not test scalability of this approach. However, by using the Twitter developer's API and collecting and analysing the data by means of an R script developed by DZHW it is possible to analyse the impact metrics of twitter channels over an extended period of time semi-automatically. With this method it is also possible to semi-automatically extract and analyse information about the Twitter profiles, which re-tweet and like the tweets in question and thus analyse a larger sample of Twitter profiles. However, the above listed issues remain, and it is questionable if the resulting analysis can be used as a meaningful indicator for assessing impact in specific stakeholder groups.

9.3.5 Lessons learned

Summarising we can say that the guidelines have proven to be useful for shaping/defining a communication strategy for a research project targeting these two large audiences. However, they do not give enough information and guidance for composing the final communication message as such.

Feedback from the ReFlex project gave us valuable feedback that allowed us to improve the guidelines further; in particular their suggestion to add an ulterior step on how to plan and implement a process to make sure that dissemination is being done in parallel to the project execution.

What could be re-evaluated and expanded is the chosen terminology and the defined scope and target groups (e.g. to include trans-disciplinary questions or guidance for addressing ulterior target groups). This does, however not lie within the scope of this project. For future research it would be relevant to explore other ways to structure the guidelines and their content to provide additional guidance for the points that our guidelines fail to provide substantial support.

Our pilot did not provide enough evidence about the measurability of impact at the targeted audiences by means of analysing likes and re-tweets by Twitter users. Our results suggest that it is not as straightforward to draw conclusions about the kind of target group Twitter users belong to. It would, however, be interesting to analyse this further with a larger dataset.

10. Appendix 3: Report on OpenUP Innovative Dissemination Training Workshop 20th June 2018, Graz

Tony Ross-Hellauer, Bianca Kramer, Jon Tennant, Michela Vignoli, Peter Kraker

<https://www.openuphub.eu/community/blog/item/report-on-openup-innovative-dissemination-training-workshop-20th-june-2018-graz>

10.1 Introduction

On 20th June 2018, in collaboration with Graz University of Technology and the University of Graz, OpenUP hosted a training workshop on “Increasing Visibility and Impact through Innovative Dissemination” in Graz, Austria. The workshop was open to early career researchers and doctoral students of all institutions. Through expert presentations and interactive breakout sessions, participants learned more about how to increase the impact of their research via novel tools and methods, including how to reach the media, industry, policymakers, and wider society. The interactive programme included talks and interactive breakout sessions from invited speakers (Bianca Kramer, Jon Tennant and Peter Kraker) and OpenUP experts (Michela Vignoli and Tony Ross-Hellauer). Members of the Graz University of Technology and University of Graz teams for publications services and public relations were also on hand to share their knowledge and learn more about how they could help their researchers.

10.2 Presentations

First Tony Ross-Hellauer gave the welcome to the workshop, introducing the OpenUP project, explaining the aims and outlining the programme ahead.

Bianca Kramer asked participants to reflect on “Where are you now?”, inviting participants to introduce themselves and explore what they are currently already doing with regards to research dissemi-

nation, what they hope to achieve and how they check whether their current strategies are actually working.

Tony Ross-Hellauer presented “10 simple rules for innovative dissemination”, explaining that research dissemination in the 21st Century isn't just articles, books and conference presentations. Open Science shows the way ahead towards dissemination that is participatory, innovative and reaches beyond the boundaries of academia.

Michela Vignoli presented “How can you reach businesses and the public? Draft guidelines by the OpenUP project”. Many researchers face challenges in terms of innovative dissemination approaches. To support researchers who are not experienced in communicating their research to businesses and the general public, in OpenUP we aim at creating recommendations and simple guidance for them on how to plan and organise their dissemination strategy accordingly. In this talk the OpenUP guidelines for communicating research to businesses and the general public will be presented and useful tips for planning your own dissemination strategy given.

Finally, Jon Tennant discussed “Using social media to build your digital profile”: Social media are a critical part of any modern researcher’s toolkit, helping them to disseminate their research and research new audiences. At the same time, this helps to enhance your career potential by diversifying your skillset and raising your public profile. Here, we will outline the top social media platforms for researchers, and how to use them to maximise your research engagement and online presence.

10.3 Breakout sessions

The afternoon invited participants to attend two of six breakout sessions on diverse themes regarding innovative dissemination.

Breakout A: “Shaping your online presence: pros, cons, and strategy” (Jon Tennant): This session focused on the different social media outlets available for researchers, and what the potential benefits and drawbacks of each might be. Attendees created their own simple social media strategies to help them maximise their online impact.

The attendees were focused on two main themes: How to share their research online to reach wider audiences, and how to communicate about that research most effectively. In particular, many decided to build a new online presence through a personal website, use of dissemination platforms like the Open Science Framework and Twitter, and also to discuss with their research supervisors what would be best overall for their research teams.

Breakout B: “What’s in it for me?” (Bianca Kramer): Sharing your research is not only of use to others, it can also bring tangible benefits for yourself. In this session we’ll explore mutual benefits of outreach at different stages of the research cycle, including how to handle feedback / criticism.

In this session, we first identified participants’ motivations for entering their chosen research fields, tapping into their personal enthusiasm about research. Participants then made a selection of dissemination practices they thought were particularly useful, and tried to define what the benefits of these would be for them personally. Finally, we discussed barriers to implementing these practices, which included personal factors like self-doubt about skills and insecurity about approaching new audiences. The practices chosen were:

- Crowdsourcing research topic prioritization
- Sharing your discovery process
- Writing collaboratively
- Archiving and sharing code
- Archiving & sharing presentations
- Presenting for the general public
- Appearing on radio/television
- Writing for general magazines/newspapers
- Presenting and giving demo’s for children (e.g. in primary/secondary education)
- Creating dedicated outreach video
- Making expertise findable, accessible, visible & available when you need it
- Creating and maintaining an online researcher profile
- Using academic social networks to find communicate with other researchers
- Making expertise findable, accessible, visible & available when you need it

The following potential (personal) benefits were identified. For some of these, we had further discussions to get from a benefit for the audience to a truly personal benefit.

- Getting funding
- Recruiting people

- Troubleshooting
- Reaching the target audience
- Structuring your work
- Recognition
- More relevant research questions
- Engaging the next generation
- Sensitize teachers & university administrators to specific issues
- Helping me to communicate complex ideas in simple ways
- Collaboration
- Help future career

Breakout C: “How do I get my research to show up in search engines and discovery tools?” (Peter Kraker): Search engines and discovery tools are how other people find your research. But how do you make sure that your publications are included in current and future services? This session provided lots of practical tips that participants can implement in no time to make sure that their research is found by their audience(s).

In this session, we focused on three main topics: (1) The benefits and limitations of current search and discovery tools such as Google Scholar and ResearchGate, (2) the inner workings of the digital open science system works and how it enables innovative services such as Open Knowledge Maps (<https://openknowledgemaps.org>), and (3) how to increase one's chances of being found in a search and discovery engines. In groups, participants discussed their own use of literature search and discovery tools and shared their findings with the group. Based on the properties of these tools, we then discussed strategies on how to maximise discoverability, including the provision of complete metadata, the use of persistent identifiers, and assigning an open license to one's output.

Breakout D: “Advantages and disadvantages of preprints and early dissemination” (Tony Ross-Hellauer): This session took a closer look at routes to the early dissemination of research outputs, specifically the use pre-prints (pre-peer review versions of academic manuscript shared freely online, often via pre-print servers like arXiv). Participants were asked to consider the advantages and difficulties of such dissemination, what differences exist across research domains, and what they could learn from each other, and which platforms, tools and practices could help.

Through interactive discussion, participants identified all the main advantages of preprints, including establishing priority, speeding dissemination, and crowdsourcing comments on early work. They also discussed how different research cultures view preprints differently, and identified some drawbacks

including that some journals discourage this practice (though it was noted this might be rather an argument in favour of changing journals than not pre-printing).

Breakout E: “Shouting louder or shouting smarter? How to get you and your research noticed” (Jon Tennant/Bianca Kramer): What happens when social media backfires? This session looked at some of the optimal ways to use digital tools to maximise the reach and impact of research. Participants discussed what works well, what to avoid, and best practices for online engagement.

Attendees all shared stories on what worked well, and sometimes not so well, to discuss key things to look out for when communicating. One common theme was to make sure to promote your work, not just yourself, and what to do if you should meet any resistance online.

Breakout F: “Reaching industry, the general public and policy-makers with your research - a role play” (Michela Vignoli): In this session we took a closer look at these target audiences and tried to understand why they are interested in research output, and how they like to receive information about research information. The participants slipped into the role of one of these target audiences as an experiment to think target group specific. Finally, the participants tested the OpenUP targeted dissemination guidelines.

The participants, divided in two groups, were asked to impersonate individuals from businesses (e.g. CEO of a big company) and policy makers (e.g. Minister for Environment) in a role play inspired setting. They had to come up with answers to the questions why these target audiences are interested in hearing about science in the first place, what information they are interested in, and for which purpose they need the information (i.e. how and in which context they plan to apply it). In this exercise the participants had to imagine being themselves part of the targeted audience, which forced them to think in line with their target audience, and not from the point of view of a researcher. The groups collected the answers on a flipchart and thus created a profile/stakeholder analysis of the target groups. In a final round the groups sat together at one table and tried applying the four steps from the draft recommendations for communicating research to businesses and the general public by OpenUP to an exemplary research project.

10.4 Wrap-up and conclusions

At the end of the workshop, participants were brought together to discuss what one concrete next step they would take towards innovative dissemination of research in the days immediately following the workshop. Their answers show that the workshop was very successful in motivating them to take up new platforms and processes:

1. Try twitter (7)
2. Post and start using pre-prints (4)
3. Try Open Knowledge Maps (3)
4. Quit Researchgate (3)
5. Self-archive papers/data/code on Zenodo with DOIs (3)
6. Create own website (2)
7. Try Open Science Framework (2)
8. Create good metadata and keywords for research outputs (2)
9. Search for alternatives to traditional publishers with restrictive practices (1)
10. Make a dissemination strategy (1)
11. Create an ORCID profile (1)
12. Create Google Scholar profile (1)
13. Share papers via Researchgate (1)
14. Learn about hashtags (1)

